

2020/2021

FINAL YEAR PROJECT

Submitted in fulfillment of the requirements for the

**ENGINEERING DEGREE FROM THE LEBANESE UNIVERSITY
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING – BRANCH III**

Major: Chemical and Petrochemical Engineering

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**OPTIMIZATION OF THE CATALYTIC DEGRADATION
OF WASTES IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY BY
COUPLING PHOTOCATALYSIS AND FENTON
PROCESS**

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The research done within this project is an exploitation of the results and techniques developed and achieved within the Horizon 2020 project CLAIM: “Cleaning Litter by developing and Applying Innovative Methods in european seas”.

CLAIM focuses on the development of innovative cleaning technologies and approaches, targeting the prevention and in situ management of visible and invisible marine litter in the Mediterranean and Baltic Sea.

I would like to thank the Scientific Research Center in Engineering (CRSI) of the Lebanese University, Faculty of Engineering, represented by the Dean Rafic Younes and Clovis Francis, CRSI Director, for hosting my research activities.

This research work is supervised by Prof. Wael Hamd, one of the main actors of the H2020 project CLAIM at the Lebanese University Faculty of Engineering.

Summary

Wastewater effluents from petroleum refineries and petrochemical plants pass through a train of treatment processes. Primary, secondary and tertiary treatments are employed for the sake of removing a wide range of pollutants. However, they are limited by treatment efficiency for certain pollutants, specifically recalcitrant organic pollutants. Effluents containing such pollutants can't be treated using the old conventional methods.

Adopting Advanced oxidation processes such as photocatalysis and Fenton processes as innovative, environmentally friendly, facile, and cost-effective technologies shall provide the route of an effective treatment. The main purpose of this project is to optimize the essential parameters influencing the activity of each process: photocatalysis and Fenton. This will be followed by the examination of the coupling between these two processes.

For the aim of the proposed project, zinc oxide was chosen as the photocatalyst material. It was synthesized and prepared by the sol-gel method followed by dip-coating on a glass substrate to create *ZnO* thin film. To test the effect of the photoactivity of the prepared photocatalyst on the kinetics of the photodegradation three parameters were altered and observed, the precursor's concentration, post-heat treatment temperature, and the number of coated layers. The best configuration obtained for this photocatalyst according to its photodegradation efficiency and the rate was the thin film prepared using a sol of $[ZAD] = 0.1M$, and by coating three layers, such that after each layer pre-heat treatment temperature applied is $150^{\circ}C$ for seven minutes, and finally post-heat treatment at $450^{\circ}C$ for one hour.

For the Fenton process section, the tested parameters were H_2O_2 concentration, catalyst (Fe^{3+}) concentration and chelating agent (*EDTA*) addition at neutral *pH*. The optimized configuration was to use 59 ppm H_2O_2 , 10 ppm Fe^{3+} and a 1:1 molar ratio of $Fe^{3+}:EDTA$.

Finally, comparison between all the optimized processes: three layers *ZnO* thin-film, photo Fenton-like process, photo Fenton-like process modified with *EDTA*, photo Fenton-like process coupled with three layers *ZnO* thin-film and photo Fenton-like process modified with *EDTA* coupled with three layers *ZnO* thin-film.

The photocatalytic degradation process experimented on 10 ppm methylene blue while the Fenton process and the coupling experimented on 20 ppm of the same probe molecule. *UV* rays ($\lambda = 366nm$) are used as the light source in all experiments. The experimental time was monitored at an interval of 30 minutes and 10 minutes in some cases.

As a final result, the photo Fenton process modified with the chelating agent showed the greatest degradation efficiency and rate, followed by the coupling of the photo Fenton process and three layers *ZnO* thin film which has shown a degradation activity greater than each process alone.

Keywords: Petroleum refineries and petrochemical plants wastewater, wastewater treatment plant, Advanced oxidation processes, Photocatalysis, Photo Fenton process, Fenton-Like process, dip-coating, layers, neutral pH, chelating agent, coupling.

Table of Contents

Acknowledgment.....	1
Summary.....	2
Table of Contents.....	3
List of Tables.....	6
List of Figures	7
List of Abbreviations and Symbols	10
General Introduction	11
1 Wastewater From the Downstream Sector	12
1.1 Introduction.....	12
1.2 Sources of wastewater.....	13
1.2.1 Crude Desalting:	13
1.2.2 Sour Water.....	14
1.2.3 Tank Bottom Draws:	17
1.2.4 Polymers.....	17
1.2.5 Spent Caustics.....	18
1.2.6 Heat Exchanger Leaks.....	19
1.2.7 Tankers.....	19
1.2.8 Others.....	19
1.2.8.1 Housekeeping and Washdowns	19
1.2.8.2 Laboratory Wastewater.....	19
1.2.8.3 Stormwater.....	19
1.3 Effects on health and environment.....	19
1.4 Treatment techniques	21
1.4.1 Process Wastewater Pretreatment.....	22
1.4.1.1 Desalter Effluent Treatment.....	22
1.4.1.2 Sour Water Stripping.....	23
1.4.1.3 Reduction and Recovery of Hydrocarbons from Wastewater at Source.....	23
1.4.2 Primary Treatment	23
1.4.2.1 First Stage: Separation (Oil/Water Separators, API Separators).....	24
1.4.2.2 Second Stage: Further Oil/Water/Solid Separation.....	24
1.4.2.2.1 Dissolved Gas Floatation	25

1.4.2.2.2	Induced Gas Flotation.....	25
1.4.3	Equalization system.....	26
1.4.4	Secondary treatment.....	26
1.4.4.1	Suspended Growth Processes.....	26
1.4.4.2	Attached Growth Processes.....	27
1.4.5	Tertiary treatment.....	28
2	Advanced Oxidation Processes	29
2.1	Principles and Fundamentals of Photocatalysis.....	29
2.1.1	Mechanism of Photocatalysis.....	30
2.1.2	Factors Influencing Photocatalytic Activity.....	31
2.1.2.1	Catalyst Loading	31
2.1.2.2	Pollutant Concentration	32
2.1.2.3	Intensity And Wavelength of Light	32
2.1.2.4	<i>pH</i>	32
2.1.2.5	Surface Area and Morphology	33
2.1.3	Zinc Oxide (<i>ZnO</i>) as Photocatalyst.....	33
2.1.4	Preparation Technique of <i>ZnO</i> Photocatalyst.....	33
2.2	Principles and Fundamentals of Fenton Process	36
2.2.1	Mechanism of Fenton Process.....	36
2.2.2	Photo Fenton Processes.....	38
2.2.3	Factors Influencing Fenton/Photo Fenton Process Activity	38
2.2.3.1	The Initial Concentration of Pollutants	38
2.2.3.2	The Concentration of Fenton Reagents (Fe^{2+}, H_2O_2)	38
2.2.3.3	<i>pH</i>	39
2.2.3.4	Temperature.....	40
2.2.4	Chelating Agents' Usage for Photo Fenton Process Enhancement.....	40
2.2.4.1	Importance of Photo Fenton-like.....	41
2.2.4.2	Choice of Chelating Agent.....	42
2.2.5	Choice of Probe Molecule	42
3	Experimental Degradation of Methylene Blue by <i>ZnO</i> Photocatalyst and photo Fenton-like Process	43
3.1	<i>ZnO</i> thin-film on a glass substrate	43
3.1.1	Materials.....	43
3.1.2	Techniques Used for the Synthesis and Characterization of <i>ZnO</i> Thin-Film	

3.1.2.1	The Dip-coating Technique.....	44
3.1.2.2	The UV/Vis Spectroscopy Technique.....	45
3.1.2.3	Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).....	46
3.1.3	Synthesis Of <i>ZnO</i> Thin-film.....	48
3.1.3.1	Preparation of Sol.....	48
3.1.3.1.1	The Choice of the Precursor.....	48
3.1.3.1.2	The Choice of the Solvent.....	48
3.1.3.1.3	The Choice of the Additive.....	48
3.1.3.2	The Dip-coating Process.....	49
3.1.3.3	The Heat Treatment Process.....	50
3.1.4	Photocatalytic Degradation of Methylene Blue by <i>ZnO</i> thin-film.....	51
3.1.4.1	Experimental Setup.....	51
3.1.4.2	Analytical Methods.....	51
3.1.4.3	Results and Discussion.....	52
3.1.4.3.1	Optical and Microstructural Properties of <i>ZnO</i> Thin-film.....	52
3.1.4.3.2	Effect of precursor's concentration.....	55
3.1.4.3.3	Effect of Post-heat Treatment Temperature.....	56
3.1.4.3.4	Degradation of methylene blue using multi-layered <i>ZnO</i> thin films	57
3.1.5	Conclusion.....	58
3.2	Photo Fenton-Like Process for Methylene Blue Degradation at Neutral <i>pH</i>	59
3.2.1	Materials.....	59
3.2.2	Experimental Setup.....	59
3.2.3	Results and Discussion.....	59
3.2.3.1	Effect of Light.....	59
3.2.3.2	Effect of H_2O_2 concentration.....	60
3.2.3.3	Effect of Fe^{3+} concentration effect.....	63
3.2.3.4	Addition of Chelating Agent.....	65
3.2.4	Conclusion.....	66
3.3	Coupling.....	67
3.3.1	Results and Discussion.....	67
3.3.2	Conclusion.....	69
	Conclusion and Future Perspectives.....	70
	BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	71

List of Tables

Table 1.1 Characteristics of desalting process wastewater	13
Table 1.2 Representative concentrations of organic pollutants in some sour water producers	14
Table 1.3 Emission and consumption data per ton of product.....	18
Table 1.4 Health and environmental effects of some petrochemical hydrocarbon pollutants.....	20
Table 1.5 Reported emissions to water observed in 98 EU refineries	21
Table 1.6 Achieved results of primary treatment stage	25
Table 2.1 Thin-Film deposition preparation methods	34

List of Figures

Figure 1.1 Typical two-stage desalter configuration [12].....	13
Figure 1.2 Simplified flow diagram of a crude desalter [9].....	13
Figure 1.3 Atmospheric and vacuum distillation flow diagram [13].....	14
Figure 1.4 Fluid catalytic cracking flow diagram [13].....	15
Figure 1.5 Catalytic hydrocracking flow diagram [13].....	15
Figure 1.6 Delayed coking flow diagram [13]	16
Figure 1.7 Visbreaking flow diagram [13]	16
Figure 1.8 Hydrotreatment flow diagram [13].....	17
Figure 1.9 Crude tank water draw [12]	17
Figure 1.10 Desalter effluent pre-treatment flow diagram [12].....	22
Figure 1.11 Single stage sour stripping unit flow diagram [12]	23
Figure 1.12 Parallel plate separator PPI [9].....	24
Figure 1.13 API Separator [9].....	24
Figure 1.14 IGF's schematic diagram	25
Figure 1.15 DGF's schematic diagram.....	25
Figure 1.16 Activated sludge system [12].....	27
Figure 1.17 Trickling filter system [12].....	27
Figure 1.18 Different Categories of AOP processes used to form complex wastewater treatment [35].....	28
Figure 2.1 Schematic diagram illustrating the principle of photocatalysis.....	30
Figure 2.2 2 Schematic representation of the typical sol-gel route.....	35
Figure 2.3 Aromatic Ring-opening due to hydroxyl radical attack	37
Figure 2.4 Speciation diagram of ferric hydroxyl-species as a function of pH [115] .39	
Figure 2.5 Comparison of Fenton and Fenton-like reactions for degradation of Acid Black 1 [104].....	41
Figure 2.6 Structure of methylene blue molecule.....	42
Figure 3.1 The HOLMARC Dip Coating Unit Model: HO-TH-02B at ULFG III Laboratory	44
Figure 3.2 The variation of film thickness as a function of withdrawal speed.....	44
Figure 3.3 Technical Drawing of the HOLMARC Dip Coating Unit Model: HO-TH-02B	45
Figure 3.4 Schematic diagram showing the working principle of a UV/Vis spectrophotometer	46

Figure 3.5 Scanning Electron Microscope setup [8].....	47
Figure 3.6 Horizontal lines formation after withdrawal at low speed.....	49
Figure 3.7 : (A): Temperature profile inside the heating chamber of the dip coater during pre-heat treatment (top), drawing of the dip-coaters heating chamber internals (bottom) (B): Temperature profile inside the furnace during post-heat treatment (top), the ceramic internals of the furnace used for post heat treatment with heating electric heating coils on the sides (bottom).....	50
Figure 3.8 The absorption of a 10 μ M methylene blue in the UV/Visible range.....	51
Figure 3.9 The absorbance (a.u.) of ZnO one layer photocatalyst before and after post-heat treatment at 350 $^{\circ}$ C.....	53
Figure 3.10 The absorbance (a.u.) of ZnO photocatalyst post-heat treated at four different temperatures	53
Figure 3.11 (A): The absorbance (a.u.) of multi-layered ZnO thin film with different number of layers, (B): Glass substrate coated with 7 layers of ZnO photocatalyst, then post-heat treated at 450 $^{\circ}$ C	54
Figure 3.12 (A): SEM micrograph of ZnO thin film at a 2 μ m scale, (B) SEM micrograph of ZnO thin film at a 500nm scale.....	55
Figure 3.13 Comparative photodegradation kinetics of 10 μ M methylene blue by ZnO thin films coated with sols of different precursor's concentration with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm.....	55
Figure 3.14 Final degradation of 10 μ M methylene blue by ZnO thin films coated with sols of different precursor's concentration with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm	56
Figure 3.15 Comparative photodegradation kinetics of 10 μ M methylene blue by ZnO thin films post-heat treated at different temperatures with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm	56
Figure 3.16 Comparative photodegradation kinetics of 10 μ M methylene blue by ZnO multilayered thin films with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm.....	57
Figure 3.17 Comparative photodegradation efficiency of methylene blue by ZnO multilayered thin films with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm.....	58
Figure 3.18 Comparative degradation rate of 10 ppm methylene blue using Fenton like and photo Fenton like process with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm.....	60
Figure 3.19 Comparative degradation efficiency of 10 ppm methylene blue by different [H ₂ O ₂]/[Fe ³⁺] ratios at different times (120,240,480) minutes with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm	61
Figure 3.20 Comparative degradation rates of 10 ppm methylene blue by different [H ₂ O ₂]/[Fe ³⁺] ratios with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm	62
Figure 3.21 The values of s found by Eq. 3.10.....	63
Figure 3.22 Comparative degradation efficiency of 10 ppm methylene blue by different Fe ³⁺ concentrations with UV light of $\lambda=365$ nm.....	63

Figure 3.23 Comparative degradation rate of 10 ppm methylene blue by different $Fe3+$ concentrations with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$	64
Figure 3.24 Top view of (A) photo Fenton-like batch reactor with 1 ppm $Fe3+$, (B) photo Fenton-like batch reactor with 10 ppm $Fe3+$ after one hour from starting the degradation of 10 ppm methylene blue with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$.....	64
Figure 3.25 Comparative degradation rate of 10ppm methylene blue using Photo Fenton-like and Photo Fenton-like with EDTA with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$ during the first one hour of the experiment.....	65
Figure 3.26 Comparative degradation rate of 10ppm methylene blue using Photo Fenton-like at two temperatures(23°C and 30°C) with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$..	66
Figure 3.27 (A): comparative degradation efficiency, and (B): comparative degradation rate of 10ppm methylene blue using Photo Fenton-like, ZnO photocatalyst and the coupling of both with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$.....	67
Figure 3.28 Comparative degradation rate from (A):0 to 60 minutes, (B): 90 to 270 minutes, (C): 300 to 480 minutes of 10 ppm MB using photo Fenton-like, ZnO photocatalyst and coupling of both with and without EDTA with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$.....	68
Figure 3.29 Comparative photograph showing samples from each process and the degradation efficiencies of 10ppm methylene blue with UV light with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$.....	69

List of Abbreviations

AOP	Advance oxidation process	USEPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency
BPCD	Barrels per calendar day	UV	Ultraviolet
BOD	Biological oxygen demand	VB	Valence band
CB	Conduction band	VOC	Volatile organic components
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics	WHO	World Health Organization
COD	Chemical oxygen demand	WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant
DAF	Dissolved air floatation	ZAD	Zinc Acetate Dihydrate
DGF	Dissolved gas floatation		
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid		
IAF	Induced air floatation		
IGF	Induced gas floatation		
LPG	Liquified Petroleum Gas		
MB	Methylene Blue		
MEA	Monoethanolamine		
MTBE	Methyl tert-butyl ether		
NTA	Nitrilotriacetic acid		
OA	Oxalic acid		
PRPP	Petroleum refineries and petrochemical plants		
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy		
SRU	Sulfur recovery unit		
TA	Tartaric acid		
TOC	Total organic carbon		
TPH	Total petroleum hydrocarbons		
TSS	Total suspended solids		

General Introduction

Water is a crucial resource for humans as it's used for drinking and household needs, recreation, industry and commerce, agriculture, and thermoelectricity/energy generation. However huge amounts of wastewater are generated due to such vast demand. This issue is currently being elucidated by constantly evolving wastewater treatment technologies, where these technologies are decisive to bring down the concentration of the contaminants to meet the reuse or discharge standards set by environmental agencies (United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), World Health Organization (WHO), etc. . .).

Water effluents from refineries and petrochemical plants are one of the streams that have to be purified before being released into the environment or even recycled through the processes [1]. The wastewater generated in Petroleum refineries and petrochemical plants (PRPP) is 0.4 to 1.6 times the volume of the oil being processed [2]. Therefore, large volumes of organic pollutants and hazardous compounds are going to be released into the environment. Due to the complexity of processes and different types of operations, complex matrices of organic pollutants are going to be formed in wastewater streams. For this reason, efficient wastewater treatment plants are needed to meet legislator's new demands and regulations. Although reaching these limits is achievable, high costs are needed (3-5% of the price of a refinery) [1]. Hence, conventional water treatment processes in PRPP are not sufficient to reach such strict limits. New methods and technologies become a necessity to achieve a relatively clean effluents that are approved to be released to environment or even reused.

Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are rapidly emerging technologies in the wastewater treatment field, and they are used for organic pollutant destruction, biodegradability improvement, and odor color removal. Such processes are needed due to some recalcitrant pollutants that are characterized by high chemical stability and can't be mineralized using biological processes. More precisely AOPs utilize very active hydroxyl radicals for the degradation of pollutants at nearly ambient conditions [3]. For these radicals to be generated two key players must exist simultaneously, an oxidant such as ozone and H_2O_2 and a catalyst (Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and ZnO), ultrasonic insertion and or thermal input. The source of hydroxyl radical generation dictates the classification of an AOP [4].

This project aims to integrate photocatalysis using zinc oxide and Fenton process for the sake of dissolved organic pollutants removal. The coming chapters include a thorough literature review for an understanding of PRPP wastewater sources, characteristics, and environmental impact. In addition to a review about wastewater treatment processes to understand better their differences and why such new technologies are needed. After the review, the laboratory work that was done will be presented in-depth where the optimization and enhancement of the photocatalyst and Fenton process took place, in addition to the coupling system between both AOPs. Finally, a conclusion and future perspectives will be presented.

1 Wastewater From the Downstream Sector

1.1 Introduction

Crude oil and natural gas transformation into useful products through PRPP is a complex and energy-intensive operation that utilizes different large-scale physical and chemical processes. These processes aim to reduce the volume of low-value products and ensure the maximum value to be obtained from used resources [5]. Gasoline, jet fuels, distillate fuel oil, and others are produced through petroleum refineries. On the other hand, polymers, aromatics, olefins are produced through petrochemical plants [6]. According to British petroleum, in 2020 total world refineries throughput was 75,512 thousand billion barrels per calendar day (BPCD) and the total production of natural gas was 3853.7 bcm of natural gas [7]. Moreover, 12 million barrels per day of oil products and 105 billion cubic meters of natural gas enter the petrochemicals sector as feedstock [8].

Consequently, it's impossible to avoid the production of significant volumes of byproducts while processing these large amounts of feedstocks. Sulfur contaminants, carbon dioxide, contaminated water, volatile organic compounds are all examples of hazardous byproducts that can have a massively damaging impact on the environment if not treated correctly [5]. Accordingly, pollution and more specifically water pollution are one of the main concerns in these industries.

To maintain the water balance in refineries and petrochemical plants, water is consumed on daily basis for several purposes, such as steam generation, cooling water, emergency fire water supply, in addition to processes and maintenance uses [9]. As a result, large amounts of wastewater are generated from different sources. Moreover, some of these effluents were in contact with hydrocarbons, which introduce to water hazardous materials that have adverse effects on both human health and the environment.

The variety of wastewater sources dictate the variety of wastewater treatment techniques and systems to account for all the pollutants and contaminants that might exist in the water. In a typical refinery or petrochemical plant, wastewater plants consist of primary and secondary treatments that are based on physicochemical methods and further biological treatments. And yet, these processes are not enough to degrade recalcitrant aromatic fractions and aliphatic hydrocarbons that are more toxic. Therefore, more advanced techniques, considered as tertiary treatment, are still a necessity to decreasing these pollutants concentrations to the lowest possible levels [10].

This chapter gives a detailed analysis of the sources and composition of PRPP wastewater, health effects, and environmental damage caused by these pollutants, methods, and steps involved in the treatment of the wastewater being discharged from oil refineries and advanced techniques developed to deal with wastewater for improved treatment.

1.2 Sources of wastewater

1.2.1 Crude Desalting:

Before entering the first unit in a refinery, crude oil is subjected to desalting (*Figure 1.1 & 1.2*) to remove components responsible for corrosion, plugging, and fouling of equipment besides catalyst poisoning. Crude is washed with water to collect all the dissolved salt crystals, this is achieved by mixing water and crude at different stages of the process [11].

Figure 1.1 Typical two-stage desalter configuration [12]

Figure 1.2 Simplified flow diagram of a crude desalter [9]

Therefore, the used wash water effluent will contain several hydrocarbons and organic molecules (*Table I-1*) as a result of this mixing. The discharged wastewater is taken to the wastewater treatment plant at the end [12].

Table 1.1 Characteristics of desalting process wastewater

Contaminant	Expected Concentration (mg/L)
Chemical Oxygen demand (COD)	400 to 1000
Free hydrocarbons	Up to 1000
Phenol	10 to 100
Benzene	5 to 15

1.2.2 Sour Water

Steam has several uses in a refinery, for example, it's used as a stripping medium in distillation and a diluent in catalytic cracking to reduce hydrocarbon partial pressure. Consequently, condensing this used steam will yield an effluent saturated in organic pollutants, sulfide (H_2S) and ammonia (NH_3) which is called "sour water"[12]. For organic pollutants, mainly phenols exist in these effluents due to the fact that they are the product of steam's reaction with cyclic hydrocarbons [1]. Moreover, the amount and composition of sour water (Table I-2) that exist in a refinery is a function of units being used. For instance, refineries that are more complex for having catalytic crackers and delayed cokers produce more sour water, which also has higher phenol and cyanide content. On the other hand, sour water from steam crackers contains aldehydes, acetic acid besides phenol [12],[1],[13].

Table 1.2 Representative concentrations of organic pollutants in some sour water producers

Unit	pH [1]	Oil [9]	Phenols [1], [9]	COD/TOC [9]
Atmospheric distillation	6-7	<50 mg/L	<50 mg/L 10-30 mg/L	50-500 mg/L
Vacuum distillation	6-7	<50 mg/L	<50 mg/L 5-10 mg/L	50-500 mg/L
Catalytic cracker	8-9.5	<50 mg/L	50-500 mg/L 80-300 mg/L	50-500 mg/L
Hydrotreater	5-6		10-20 mg/L	
Hydrocracker	6-8.5	<50 mg/L	-	<50 mg/L

A vast amount of water is consumed during the crude distillation process, by combining vacuum and atmospheric distillation, the resultant sour water effluent is estimated as 26 gallons per barrel of oil [13]. This oily wastewater is produced from side stripping fractionators and reflux drums as shown in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3 Atmospheric and vacuum distillation flow diagram [13]

Unlike previous processes, coking produces less amount of wastewater, three gallons per barrel of process feed, knowing that in addition to fractionators and steam strippers, coke removal also generates wastewater (Fig. 1.6)

Figure 1.6 Delayed coking flow diagram [13]

In the Visbreaking process, the main source of sour water is the fractionator overhead drum as shown in Figure 1.7 where it's separated from a hydrocarbon gas stream and hydrocarbon liquid stream. This stream contains phenols in the range of 5 to 30 ppm and 50-100 ppm free oils [9].

Figure 1.7 Visbreaking flow diagram [13]

Same as other processes, sour water in a hydrotreatment process is generated in the fractionator (*Figure 1.8*), approximately 8-14.5 gallons per ton of feed [9]

Figure 1.8 Hydrotreatment flow diagram [13]

1.2.3 Tank Bottom Draws:

Wastewater could also originate from the bottom of crude and gasoline tanks, owing to the fact that crude normally contains water, and when stored this water settles to the bottom leading to a loss in storage capacity.

Figure 1.9 Crude tank water draw [12]

Therefore, this water is removed periodically, however, drainage from gasoline tanks is lower than that in crude tanks. Moreover, this drained water has been in contact with hydrocarbons, for that reason it has a COD concentration of 400 to 1000 mg/L. [12]

1.2.4 Polymers

In our daily lives, polymers are used extensively such as in clothing, packaging, tires, and many more other uses. This vast range of polymer usages dictates a huge demand for this material in its different types and varieties. In general, polymerization is the step where

monomers are transformed into polymers, then these polymers turn into user-end products after processing. These processes consume water for cooling and as process feed, therefore wastewater will be generated with a certain concentration of pollutants and organic material. In the following table water consumption, COD, and wastewater emissions for some processes are shown.

Table 1.3 Emission and consumption data per ton of product

Polymer	Water consumption	COD emission	References
Polyolefins			
Low-density polyethylene (LDPE)	2.9 m ³	62 g	[14, p. 62]
High-density polyethylene (HDPE)	2.3 m ³	67 g	[14, p. 64]
Linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE)	1.8 m ³	68 g	[14, p. 65]
Polystyrene			
General-purpose polystyrene (GPS)	50.596 t	40 g	[14, p. 84]
High impact polystyrene (HIPS)	50.519 t	40 g	[14, p. 86]
Expandable polystyrene (EPS)	19.1 t	-	[14, p. 88]
Unsaturated polyesters	13m ³	140 g	[14, p. 115]
Emulsion polymerized Styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR)	5-20 m ³	150-200 g	[14, p. 126]
Solution polymerized rubber containing butadiene	-	430-1250 g	[14, p. 136]
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) fibers			
Continuous polycondensation base on dimethyl terephthalic acid (DMT)	0.1-2.15 m ³	8000-16000 g	[14, p. 170]
Continuous polycondensation based on terephthalic acid (TPA)	0.4-10 m ³	2000-16000 g	
Batch polycondensation based on DMT	7.5-122 m ³	3000-5210 g	
PET processing			
Stable fibers	1.14-15 m ³	14,841 g	[14, p. 171]
Filaments yarns	0.5-35.2 m ³	4157 g	

1.2.5 Spent Caustics

Some hydrocarbon streams need to be treated from acidic components and mercaptans therefore caustic extraction is applied. Gasoline sweetening process (Mercox), or alkaline washing of Liquified Petroleum Gas (LPG) and kerosene uses such extraction and generates spent caustic effluents [1]. Therefore, such effluents might contain sulfides, mercaptans, sulfates, sulfonates, phenolates, naphthenates, and several other similar organic pollutants [15]. Moreover, treating with caustic the corrosive crude, specifically the kerosene/jet fuel cut where naphthenic acids tend to concentrate lead the acids to be transformed into naphthenates, which are refractory to biological treatments [12].

1.2.6 Heat Exchanger Leaks

In refineries heating or cooling are both essential for streams treatment and conditioning before introducing it into units. For this purpose, water is used for heating (steam) or cooling by heat exchangers organized in closed loops. However, these heat exchangers may encounter some leakage due to the pressure difference between the water/ steam stream and the process stream. For this reason, the used water will be subjected to contamination with hydrocarbons leading it to be categorized as wastewater when discharge from the process (cooling tower blowdown, boiler blowdown, steam generator blowdown....) [1], [12].

1.2.7 Tankers

Wastewater could also be generated due to operations in oil tankers such as maintenance and DE-ballasting. Periodic maintenance of tankers requires cleaning using high water flows mixed with detergents and caustic soda. Therefore, stable emulsions of hydrocarbons in water are going to be formed generating wastewater to be treated. Tanks that ship intermediate and final products discharge ballast water. Although this water is used for providing stability, DE-ballasting water has certain concentrations of dissolved hydrocarbons present from various refined products, in addition to a hydrocarbon content of 50 to 100 ppm leading this operation to be a source of wastewater [1].

1.2.8 Others

1.2.8.1 Housekeeping and Washdowns

Wastewater could also originate from washdown process areas, in addition to hydrocarbon spills and other materials [12].

1.2.8.2 Laboratory Wastewater

Each refinery has its laboratory to analyze hydrocarbon and water samples, generate wastewater that could contain hydrocarbons, chemicals, and solvents used during tests [12].

1.2.8.3 Stormwater

Stormwater refers to rainfall or snowfall that precipitates in the refinery process area. This water can be potentially contaminated and has a high flow rate that could reach $3000 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. To treat this water efficiently, it's stored and treated at low flow rates [1], [12].

1.3 Effects on health and environment

Given the number of sources PRPP wastewater can come from during production processes, water may be highly contaminated with various pollutants, consequently, this water is a major contributor to ground and surface water contamination. Taking no action to deal with these effluents, could possess a serious risk to human health and the environment due to different toxic chemicals that might exist.

These hazards have caused increased concern for communities around them resulting in several environmental laws related to water. Some regulations that control water pollution due to refineries include the Clean Water Act, the Safe Drinking Water Act, OSHA (Occupational Safety & Health Administration), TSCA (Toxic substances Control Act).

PRPP wastewater contains a complex matrix of pollutants, and they are in the form of oil, gas, wax, grease, metals, minerals, hydrocarbons [16]. Furthermore, the main hydrocarbons

that exist in PRPP wastewater in large quantities are polycyclic and aromatic, phenols, surfactants, and other chemicals [17]. Undoubtedly, the release of these chemicals will influence human health and the environment. For instance, it has been proven that aromatic organic compounds cause carcinogenic and mutagenic damage [18]. Even if a human has no direct exposure to this wastewater, these pollutants could still be transferred to him by the food chain through infected food that was previously exposed to this water [19]. Several toxic consequences on human health could be produced due to his consumption of contaminated food [20].

Moreover, plants' and animals' growth are also influenced if PRPP wastewater was used for irrigation due to the changes that would occur on the soil upon its exposure to wastewater followed by respiration and photosynthesis inhibition of plants and microorganisms [16], [21]. *Table 1.4* summarizes some of the petrochemical hydrocarbon pollutants that could exist in wastewater with their health and environmental effect in addition to WHO guideline values for drinking water.

Table 1.4 Health and environmental effects of some petrochemical hydrocarbon pollutants

Contaminant	Effect On Humans	Effect On Environment	Guideline Values That are of Health Significance in Drinking Water (Mg/l)
<i>Phenol</i>	Gastrointestinal irritation, painless blanching, erythema, deep necrosis, cardiac dysrhythmias, respiratory distress, renal failure, neurological effects, coma, death [22]	Toxic for aquatic organisms, transported by wet deposition and by leaching through soil [22]	2 [23]
<i>Benzene</i>	Carcinogenic, aplastic anemia, Chromosomal aberrations and mutations (in vitro) [24]	If it's release into water it will be rapidly volatilized. Therefore it will not significantly adsorb to sediment, bioconcentrate in aquatic organisms or hydrolyze [25]	0.01 [26]
<i>Toluene</i>	Neurological effects, encephalopathy, optic atrophy, equilibrium disorders [27]	Inhibit photosynthesis and respiration of some marine communities [27], damage to ozone layer [18]	0.7 [26]
<i>Ethylbenzene</i>	Irreversible damage to hearing, kidney damage, carcinogenic [28]	Negative effects on aquatic life [29]	0.3 [26]

1.4 Treatment techniques

The configuration of any wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) depends on the characteristics of the wastewater and the desired quality to be reached [30]. Accordingly, techniques used for treating PRPP wastewater differ from the ones used for urban wastewater or other industrial wastewater. For the same reason, technologies used for refinery wastewater systems are site-specific [12]. Furthermore, PRPP wastewater holds a very complex matrix of pollutants, as a result, different types of treatment are needed for the sake of reaching the stringent regulations and alter the water quality to be suitable for discharge or recycle. The table below (*Table I-5*) shows the variety of pollutants that exist in wastewater from refineries.

Table I.5 Reported emissions to water observed in 98 EU refineries

Parameter	Average concentration (mg/L)	Average Relative load (g/tonne)	Parameter	Average concentration (mg/L)	Relative load (g/tonne)
BOD	8.62	11.83	Chlorides	548.25	641.41
COD	59	106.35	Fluorides	1.23	0.93
TOC	13.62	15.94	Free Cyanides	0.02	0.02
TSS	63.09	180.54	Nitrates	8.15	7.08
TPH	1.83	2.68	Nitrites	0.77	1.33
Benzene	0.02	0.02	Sulfides	0.08	0.08
Toluene	0.02	0.02	Sulphites	7.31	34.56
Ethylbenzene	0.01	0.01	Total Nitrogen	8.92	9.02
Xylenes	0.03	0.02	Total Phosphorus	0.55	0.48
Phenol index	0.08	0.08	Arsenic	0.01	0.01
MTBE	0.05	0.08	Cadmium	1.83×10^{-3}	3.04×10^{-4}
Naphthalene	9.5×10^{-4}	1.17×10^{-3}	Chromium	0.01	0.01
Anthracene	6.33×10^{-5}	7.49×10^{-5}	Chromium (VI)	0.02	0.02
Fluoranthene	8.13×10^{-5}	8.92×10^{-5}	Cobalt	2.55×10^{-3}	3.05×10^{-3}
Benzo(a)pyrene	3.34×10^{-5}	4.7×10^{-5}	Copper	0.01	0.01
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	4.49×10^{-5}	1.33×10^{-4}	Iron	0.42	0.56
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	4.45×10^{-5}	5.94×10^{-6}	Lead	0.01	0.01
Dichloromethane	2.47×10^{-3}	3.74×10^{-5}	Nickel	0.02	0.02
Trichloromethane	1.22×10^{-3}	1.22×10^{-3}	Selenium	0.02	0.02
Ammonia	2.71	3.14	Zinc	0.06	0.06

PRPP wastewater treatment is classified as follows [9], [12], [13], [31]–[33]:

- process wastewater pretreatment;
- primary treatment;
- secondary treatment;
- tertiary treatment

1.4.1 Process Wastewater Pretreatment

Some units might generate wastewater that couldn't be discharged directly to treatment due to its negative impact on the equipment to be used later. Therefore, pretreatment is a necessity for these effluents before proceeding with their treatment [12]. Some practices that are being used as pretreatment are:

1.4.1.1 Desalter Effluent Treatment

Wastewater from a desalter could contain oil, emulsions, and solids in addition to significant concentrations of volatile organic components (VOCs) leading to excessive emissions and odor problems. For this reason, this effluent is sent to a floating roof tank (*Figure 1.10*) which will have a residence time of 24 hours to allow phase separation.

Figure 1.10 Desalter effluent pre-treatment flow diagram [12]

Then, oil is skimmed from the top, water is sent for treatment, and solids are sent to waste treatment or coker unit. A floating tank is used to avoid pressure increase in the separation tank due to VOC accumulation. Furthermore, controlling VOCs in this effluent might dictate installing steam or natural gas strippers on the water stream before entering the WWTP to avoid entering high concentrations of oil and solids into the stripping unit [12].

1.4.1.2 Sour Water Stripping

As shown in figure 1.11, sour water streams discussed earlier, are all collected in a vessel to provide hold up for a feed and facilitate oil/water separation. Also, pH control is applied to enhance H_2S and NH_3 removal.

Figure 1.11 Single stage sour stripping unit flow diagram [12]

Then, in a stripping column sour water is counter currently stripped by steam. Sour-off-gases can be routed to a Sulfur recovery unit (SRU), stripped water is routed for recycling in the refinery or WWTP [1], [9], [12]. Sour water stripping could be done in one stage or two stages. Although most used sour strippers are single staged the two-stage stripping yields much lower H_2S and NH_3 concentrations [9].

1.4.1.3 Reduction and Recovery of Hydrocarbons from Wastewater at Source

Instead of mixing wastewater and having a wide range of pollutants, benzene, phenols, and hydrocarbons in wastewater can be often treated more efficiently at the source point. This could be done by different techniques [9]:

- nitrogen or air stripping for benzene recovery from wastewater;
- liquid-Liquid extraction for phenol extraction from wastewater using for example butyl acetate as a solvent;
- high-pressure wet air oxidation where treatment is done at high temperature ($250^{\circ}C$) and pressure of 7 MPa;
- low-pressure oxidation (2 MPa), integrated with biological treatment.

1.4.2 Primary Treatment

Primary treatment consists mainly of physical operations, like gravity separation, to remove heterogeneous components found in effluents such as suspended solids (SS), solid particles, and immiscible liquids. In a typical refinery, primary treatment is divided into two stages. The purpose of the first stage is to separate and extract insoluble hydrocarbons, and the purpose of the second is to improve the solid/liquid or liquid/liquid separation of the remaining hydrocarbons and suspended solids (SS) in the effluent of step one, however, some chemicals are used in this step, therefore this step is considered a physicochemical process [9], [12].

1.4.2.1 First Stage: Separation (Oil/Water Separators, API Separators)

To achieve the foreseen purpose of this stage the principle of specific gravity difference is utilized, therefore the settling will occur to the phase with the highest density and the less dense phase will float on the surface. Accordingly, hydrocarbons float on the surface and are skimmed constantly, while sludge will settle and be removed periodically.

This stage might include:

- parallel plate interceptors (PPIs) (Figure 1.12);
- API separators (APIs) (Figure 1.13);
- corrugated plate interceptors (CPIs);
- tilted plate interceptors (TPIs);
- equalization tanks

Figure 1.12 Parallel plate separator PPI [9]

1. Trash trap (inclined rods)
2. Oil retention baffles
3. Flow distributors
4. Oil layer
5. Slotted pipe skimmer
6. Adjustable overflow weir
7. Sludge sump
8. Chain and flight scraper

Figure 1.13 API Separator [9]

1.4.2.2 Second Stage: Further Oil/Water/Solid Separation

Entering biological treatment immediately after the first stage of primary treatment will cause improper operation, due to the remaining high concentration of nonbiodegradable SS and insoluble hydrocarbons. Hence a second stage is necessary to remove finer solids and emulsified oil [1], [9]. Besides the physical separation to be done at this stage, chemicals are added to induce two phenomena, coagulation, and flocculation. Coagulation is done by introducing a coagulant to break the electrostatic bonds of colloid and also break up fine hydrocarbon emulsion. Then a flocculant is added to grow the oily flocs formed due to coalescence so that they could be removed by mechanical separation [1].

This stage might include:

- dissolved gas floatation (DGF);
- induced gas floatation (IGF)

1.4.2.2.1 Dissolved Gas Flotation

DGF (Figure 1.14) uses gas bubbles to promote the rising of the flocs formed earlier to the surface to be skimmed. The gas bubbles are formed by recycling part of the treated water under pressure and dissolving gas till saturation then mixing it with the feed. Depressurizing the recycled stream releases the gas bubbles which attach themselves to any free oil/ solids present in the feed and float them on the surface of the vessel. Floated material is then skimmed and sent to refinery slops [1], [9], [34].

1.4.2.2.2 Induced Gas Flotation

In this technique, very large gas bubbles are formed due to applying very high mixing energy, supplied by a spinning rotor. The performance of this technique is inferior to DGF, however, the advantages of IGF are compact size and low capital cost [1], [12]. Figure 1.15 shows a typical schematic diagram of IGF.

Figure 1.15 DGF's schematic diagram

Figure 1.14 IGF's schematic diagram

In other industries, these techniques are called Dissolved air flotation (DAF) and Induced air flotation (IAF) since the gas used is air. But due to the potential accumulation of explosive vapors released from PRPP, gases are used to mitigate the risk [9]. Table 1.6 shows the achieved results on both stages [9].

Table 1.6 Achieved results of primary treatment stage

	Particle size	Effluent composition	Achieved oil concentration
First stage	$\geq 150 \mu\text{m}$	Insoluble dispersed oil droplets, emulsified oil droplets, suspended solids soluble inorganic substances, soluble organic substances Trace amounts of insoluble free phased hydrocarbon and settleable solids.	50 – 100 ppm
Second stage	$< 150 \mu\text{m}$	Soluble inorganic substances, soluble organic substances. Trace amounts of free oil droplets, dispersed oil droplets, settleable and suspended solids.	10 – 20 ppm

1.4.3 Equalization system

Wastewater has a variable flow and concentrations; therefore, an equalization system comes in handy to minimize potential spikes in flow and concentration to downstream processes. Flow equalization decreases the size of the downstream units in addition to the overall cost of the WWT plant. While concentration equalization mitigates contaminants' shock on the bioreactors in secondary treatment, therefore improving the effectiveness of the secondary treatment. Three positions could be considered for an equalization system, upstream of the first stage from primary separation, upstream of the second stage from secondary separation, or upstream of the secondary treatment. Each position has its unique effects on the following processes. For instance, placing this system before the first stage or second stage of primary treatment is to damp the flow fluctuations, however, certain costs are added such as hardware (piping/pump, etc....) and frequent cleaning to handle the solids and oil contained in this stream. On the other hand, positioning this system upstream of secondary treatment is to relieve the biological system from wide variations in flow and concentration [12], [33], [35].

1.4.4 Secondary treatment

The remaining dissolved oil and other organic pollutants are treated at this level of treatment. Microorganisms are the key players in such systems. They are responsible for consuming and oxidizing the organic material into simpler molecules, for example, H_2O , CH_4 and CO_2 under a different condition. Biological assimilation of soluble hydrocarbons in PRPP wastewater could be achieved by two types of processes [9], [12], [33]–[35]:

- suspended growth processes;
- attached growth processes

1.4.4.1 *Suspended Growth Processes*

The most commonly used suspended growth process for PRPP wastewater treatment is the activated sludge process (ASP) [9]. This process is the most effective compared to other biological systems [12]. The main principle of this system is that microorganisms are mixed vigorously with the organics in liquid and conserved as a suspension. Hence, the microorganisms devour organic constituents for the sake of obtaining carbon and energy to ensure their growth. Accordingly, the consumed organics are converted into cell tissue, water, and oxidized products, mainly CO_2 .

The main components of this process are an aeration tank where microorganisms develop in suspended growth in the presence of air or oxygen (Aerobic conditions), and a clarifier to separate the biomass and activated sludge from water [1]. As shown in Figure 1.16, the influent wastewater comes in contact with microorganisms and air in the aeration tank where organic contaminants get transformed into biomass. Then, the effluent is introduced to a clarifier for the sake of separating the biomass and activated sludge followed by recycling a portion of this sludge to conserve the optimum bacterial concentration in the tank.

Figure 1.16 Activated sludge system [12]

1.4.4.2 Attached Growth Processes

Instead of having the microorganisms suspended in the liquid, they could be attached to inert packing material. The microorganisms come in contact with contaminants at the surface of the media they are attached to, then convert the organics into biomass and CO_2 . One of the most used processes of this type is the trickling filter. As shown in Figure 1.17, such a system consists of a bed containing the packing material which could be rock or plastic, and distributors that ensure a good distribution of influent water over the filter bed. Then an underdrain system to carry the effluent to the next units. Similar to ASP, a clarifier exists at the end to remove excess microbial growth [12].

In the domain of biological treatment other technologies also exist, such as powdered activated carbon treatment, sequencing batch reactors, continuous stirred tank bioreactor, and membrane bioreactors, all these technologies are classified as suspended growth processes. For smaller scale treatments, attached growth processes are used such as trickling filters, fluidized bed bioreactor, and rotating biological contactor [33]. Under normal operating conditions a biodegradation system could remove 80-90% of dissolved oil and COD as well as 90%-98% BOD [9].

Figure 1.17 Trickling filter system [12]

1.4.5 Tertiary treatment

Stringent limits on certain contaminants might be required from refineries to obtain in their wastewater treatment before discharge or even recycle. Therefore, a tertiary treatment or polishing step is needed. This refers to any treatment that takes place downstream of the secondary treatment to obtain a very high-quality effluent that meets the discharge limits [33]–[35]. Tertiary treatment is traditionally achieved through sand filtration, activated carbon filtration, or chemical oxidation [12], [33]. However more recent promising technologies are emerging such as AOPs (Figure 3.18) to remove recalcitrant organic components.[31], [33], [35]–[37].

Figure 1.18 Different Categories of AOP processes used to form complex wastewater treatment [35]

AOPs target mainly low biodegradability, refractory, inhibitory, or high stability chemical pollutants [38], it converts these pollutants into simpler compounds using generated oxidizing radicals [31]. More precisely, the radicals are hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot OH$), characterized as powerful oxidants [36]. $\cdot OH$ radicals are considered highly effective and non-selective with a redox potential of 2.8 V, for this reason, these radicals are able to destroy and even mineralize pollutants into carbon dioxide and water [38]. Generation of these radicals could be done by several processes such as Fenton oxidation, photo Fenton oxidation, photocatalysis, ozone-based processes, and different combinations of these processes and others. When dealing with low concentrations, in the range below a hundred milligrams per liter, AOPs are the most suitable option to choose[39]. Although biological treatments are widely spread and are used in wastewater treatment, the organic compounds that might exist in the influent could be toxic for the microorganisms utilized, or recalcitrant. Accordingly, AOPs could be used to transform the organic pollutants into biodegradable compounds that could be handled by secondary treatment, rather than full mineralization [39].

However AOPs are considered more energy-intensive than material-intensive [39], therefore a need arises for advanced technologies for the degradation of recalcitrant organic pollutants in PRPP. And because coupling could be a satisfactory approach for reducing energy requirements and environmental impact [39] this study will discuss a strategy developed to end with the coupling of two AOPs, starting with producing and optimizing thin film photocatalysis, followed by implementing a Fenton-like process at neutral pH at an optimum concentration of involved reactants.

2 Advanced Oxidation Processes

As shown in the previous chapter persistent organic pollutants that exist in PRPP wastewater pose a threat to human health and the environment. Therefore, novel technologies and treatment techniques are needed to handle different concentrations of organic pollutants. AOPs are being recently noticed in the domain of wastewater treatment, specifically for the treatment of recalcitrant organic pollutants.

Technologies and techniques used in the primary treatment are considered physical treatment processes, therefore it's difficult for ordinary physical treatment to manage organic pollutants [40]. Although biological treatments can solve this issue, in return additional time, investment, and operating costs must be paid [41]–[43]. AOPs, which are considered as chemical processes, could be the best method to treat organic wastewater, owing to this to the fact that AOPs are highly efficient, at rapid rates with no secondary pollution [38], [44]–[46].

In this chapter, elaboration, and discussion of two examples from the AOPs, the photocatalysis, and photo Fenton process will be done, starting with principles and fundamentals followed by the mechanisms taking place and the parameters that alter the process performance. In the end, an explanation of the path chosen will be followed to implement each process.

2.1 Principles and Fundamentals of Photocatalysis

Photocatalysis stands for chemical reactions occurring in the presence of light and a photocatalyst, or as defined by IUPAC, a catalytic reaction involving light absorption by substrate [47]. Accordingly, a photocatalyst is a type of material capable of influencing the rate of a chemical reaction on exposure to light [48]. Photocatalysts are semiconductors, where this type of material is known for its capability of generating electron-hole pairs due to irradiation at a certain wavelength, in addition to, its redox potential and adsorption ability. This set of physicochemical properties makes them an appropriate material for photocatalysis [44], [49].

Photocatalytic reactions are of two types: Homogenous photocatalysis, where both semiconductor and reactant are of the same phase, and heterogeneous photocatalysis where they are of different phases [48]. Heterogeneous photocatalysis is the most frequently used technique for water treatment due to the ease of separation of the catalyst after the process is done [50]. In this study, the focus will be on heterogenous photocatalysis due to the reasons mentioned.

Semiconductors are characterized by a bandgap E_g , with a value that falls between conducting material and insulating material. The bandgap E_g represents the difference between the valence band and the conduction band [48]. Some of the advantages of semiconductor material being photocatalysts are the photoactivity in the ultraviolet (UV) and visible light, inertness in addition to low toxicity and low cost [38], [47], [51], [52].

The photocatalytic process in water can be formed of five steps [53]:

1. Transfer of reactant in water to the surface of the photocatalyst
2. Adsorption of reactants on the surface
3. Activation of the surface and reaction in the adsorbed phase
4. Desorption of reaction products
5. Elimination of reaction products from the interface region

The main objective of using photocatalysis for water treatment and considering it as an AOP is the semiconductor capability of forming hydroxyl radicals upon illumination with light of a suitable wavelength. This radical is known to be an extremely strong oxidant, non-selective and capable of mineralizing organic pollutants with no secondary pollution.

2.1.1 Mechanism of Photocatalysis

The photocatalytic reaction mechanism is explained by the following steps [44], [47], [54]–[58] in addition to the photocatalysis principle shown in Figure below:

Figure 2.1 Schematic diagram illustrating the principle of photocatalysis.

1. Generation of electron-hole pairs due to the absorption of light energy which is greater than or equal to the bandgap energy of the semiconductor. Electrons (e^-) from the valence band (VB) gets excited to the conduction band (CB), this transfer of electrons from VB to CB created holes (h^+) in the VB (Eq. 2.1).

2. Transfer of electrons and holes to the surface of the photocatalyst
3. Utilization of charges on the surface for redox reactions.

- a. Dissolved oxygen is reduced by e^- to form superoxide radicals $O_2^{\bullet-}$ (Eq. 2.2)

- b. Water is oxidized by h^+ forming hydroxyl radicals (OH^\bullet) (Eqs. 2.3 and 2.4).

- c. Direct oxidation of organic pollutants by the means of positive holes could also take place (Eq. 2.5)

- d. Further protonation of superoxide radical forms hydroperoxyl radical, and subsequently hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) (Eqs. 2.6 and 2.7)

- e. H_2O_2 reacts with superoxide radical forming hydroxyl radicals (Eq. 2.8)

4. The OH^\bullet formed from previous reactions leads to complete or partial mineralization of organic pollutants (Eq. 2.9)

2.1.2 Factors Influencing Photocatalytic Activity

2.1.2.1 Catalyst Loading

According to the previous mechanism, producing more OH^\bullet radicals and positive holes result in an increased organic pollutants mineralization. For this to occur, more catalyst sites have to be irradiated, therefore increased catalyst amount is going to facilitate pollutant's degradation rate. At a lower catalyst amount, fewer active sites to adsorb photons exist, therefore the degradation rate decreases. However, increasing catalyst dosage above a certain limit has a negative effect on photocatalytic activity, where degradation rate and activity decreases. This could be attributed to the fact that the increasing catalyst dosage forces the excess catalyst's surface to scatter the light and blocking it from reaching other active sites thereby decreasing its activity [44], [59]

2.1.2.2 Pollutant Concentration

The number of organic pollutants adsorbed onto the photocatalyst surface dictates the degradation efficiency and not the organic pollutants' concentration in the bulk. Also, high adsorption occurs when a high initial concentration of pollutants is provided therefore more pollutants molecules are oxidized, which enhances the photodegradation efficiency. However, reduction in photodegradation takes place for pollutants' initial concentration greater than a certain limit, since full coverage of catalyst surface will occur and the active sites will not absorb the required amount of light [44].

2.1.2.3 Intensity And Wavelength of Light

As mentioned earlier, the initiation of photocatalysis reaction occurs due to the absorption of light by a semiconductor. Therefore, for this light to activate the photocatalyst it must have an energy value greater than or equal to the bandgap energy of the semiconductor. Also, knowing that light's energy is inversely proportional to light's wavelength, light capable of activating a certain semiconductor must have a wavelength below a certain value to achieve the energy condition. For instance, TiO_2 has a wide bandgap which limits its absorption in the UV region [60].

Regarding the effect of light intensity, the degradation rate in relation to light intensity changes at different levels of intensity. In general, increasing light intensity will decrease the rate dependency on it, till it reaches a level where the rate reaches a certain level and increasing intensity has no effect on it. The reason for this is that the activation sites of the catalyst are constant, and all will get activated at a certain intensity [44], [60], [61].

2.1.2.4 pH

In wastewater treatment, pH is a critical factor that influences several aspects of the photocatalysis system simultaneously. Variation of pH has a direct impact on the photocatalyst surface charge. Specifically, increasing solution's pH above the isoelectric point of the photocatalyst induces a negative charge on the photocatalyst surface. Therefore, cationic pollutants favorably adsorb through electrostatic interaction. However, having a pH lower than the isoelectric point of the photocatalyst will induce positive charges on the surface, consequently, anionic pollutants adsorption will occur. Knowing that adsorption is the preliminary step for efficient photocatalysis, the pH effect on charge of the surface will directly impact pollutants adsorption then definitely affecting the pollutant's degradation efficiency.

Furthermore, photodegradation using hydroxyl radicals is dominant at high pH , on the other hand at lower pH , positive holes are mainly responsible for photodegradation. According to equation 2.4, the formation of hydroxyl radicals is favored by a high concentration of hydroxyl ions that exist at high pH values, however, these hydroxyl ions at higher pH values compete with pollutants to get adsorbed on the catalyst surface. Conversely, low pH is beneficial for anionic species degradation but not for cationic species due to their reduced adsorption. To conclude, the nature of pollutants and photocatalyst characteristics (zero-point charge pH_{pzc}) dictate the system behavior at a certain pH .

2.1.2.5 Surface Area and Morphology

The superior photocatalytic activity could be achieved if the catalyst structure was tuned correctly to become suitable for the desired application. Diverging from bulk material and leaning toward nanomaterials provide larger surface area and smaller size in the application, thereby increased final degradation [62]. Decreasing the size of the catalyst leads to the accumulation of a huge number of atoms on the surface. Hence, the number of active sites increases therefore redox reactions are enhanced [63]. However, the optimum size of the nano-catalyst is needed since beyond this size recombination of the generated electron-hole pairs increases [64], [65].

2.1.3 Zinc Oxide (ZnO) as Photocatalyst

In the past few years, *ZnO* is thoroughly researched, due to its distinctive optoelectronic, catalytic, and photochemical properties [61], [62], [66]–[68]. Although *TiO₂* is extensively used in the field of water treatment but in some case *ZnO* showed better activity than *TiO₂* [69]. *ZnO* is an environmentally friendly material, that poses no risk on humans or animals. Although, both has approximately the same band gap energy therefore their photocatalytic activity are similar, in addition to that *ZnO* is relatively cheaper than *TiO₂* [61]. Accordingly, *ZnO* will be the focus in our study and will utilized in our experimental part in the next chapter.

2.1.4 Preparation Technique of ZnO Photocatalyst

Immobilization of *ZnO* photocatalyst as a thin film on a glass substrate is adopted in this study, such method allows to surpass certain limitations of conventional heterogeneous catalysts [70]. Furthermore, one can notice the plenty of advantages that thin-film photocatalyst could offer over powdered photocatalyst, for instance, it's cost-effective due to reduction in material usage, elimination of expensive recycling, and recollection after degradation. Also, it offers better long-term performance in addition to the easiness of incorporating it in different devices [71].

The structure of the film determines the properties and qualities of the film, however, the film structure in addition to mechanical and thermal properties are highly connected to adopted preparation and deposition methods [70]–[72]. Classification of thin-film deposition methods is shown in table 2.1 below:

Table 2.1 Thin-Film deposition preparation methods

Chemical	Spray pyrolysis technique (SPT)	
	Sol-Gel method	[74]–[77]
	Chemical bath deposition (CBD)	[78]
	Successive Ionic layer adsorption and Reaction (SILAR)	[79]
	Hydrothermal	[80]
	Atomic layer deposition (ALD)	[81]
	Chemical vapor deposition (CVD)	[82]
	Electrodeposition	[83]
Physical	Sputtering	[84]
	Evaporation	[85]
	Laser evaporation (Pulse laser deposition)	[86]
	Electron beam evaporation	[87], [88]
	Arc evaporation	[89]

For our study, the sol-gel method is chosen. This method for film preparation is easy to control, low cost and demands low fabrication temperature [74]. The sol-gel process is a wet-chemical technique that enables the synthesis of heterogenous photocatalysts by starting from a colloidal suspension (sol). Sol is a suspension of solid particles whose sizes range from $1nm$ to $1\mu m$, and the stability of the suspension is maintained due to van der Waals and coulombic repulsive forces. The condensation of the particle into a three-dimensional network produces a highly viscous material (gel). Transition to solid is done by solvent removal that requires drying [70].

The formation of thin-film by sol-gel involves three steps:

- 1- Preparation of precursor solution
- 2- Deposition of sol on the substrate
- 3- Thermal treatment to the deposited film

To deposit the sol on a substrate, two techniques are available: Spin-coating and dip-coating techniques. Dip-coating is being chosen since it offers easier deposition of the large-area substrate with optimum thickness, the quality of the film is easily adjusted by optimizing dipping, drying, and retrieval time [71] The whole process is shown in Figure 2.2 below.

Figure 2.2.2 Schematic representation of the typical sol-gel route

2.2 Principles and Fundamentals of Fenton Process

Among AOPs, Fenton processes are commonly utilized for wastewater treatment. They have been widely used for the removal of recalcitrant organic pollutants [90], [91]. Fenton processes are performed at room temperature and atmospheric pressure, and these two aspects of the process increase its attractiveness to be used as a wastewater treatment. Also, the process is considered simple, easy to operate and no special equipment is needed. Furthermore, it has the shortest reaction time among AOPs [92]–[95]. Fenton processes are processes that use H_2O_2 as an oxidant and ferrous salt as a catalyst under acidic conditions for the production of hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet OH$). It's named after Henry John Horstman Fenton for his work on oxidation of tartaric acid in the presence of iron salt (1894) [96]. Even though the Fenton process is most powerful, effective and energetically efficient process compared to other AOPs [4], but it has some significant limitations: Narrow working pH range, the significant amounts iron sludge produced [38], [90], [97]–[99], and the high cost of chemicals especially H_2O_2 [92], [100], [101]. These limitations are hindering the Fenton process from being economically viable to be industrialized on larger scale. Therefore, Fenton processes are being subjected to research and development for the sake of optimization in order to develop a novel high efficiency wastewater treatment technology.

The accepted reaction that the Fenton process governs for the production of the highly oxidative hydroxyl radical ($\bullet OH$) is shown below (Eq. 2.10), where Fe^{2+} and H_2O_2 reacts under acidic conditions, to form the mentioned species and nonselectively degrade recalcitrant organic pollutants to carbon dioxide and water [97].

The rate and degradation efficiency of a Fenton process are highly dependent on different operation parameters, such as wastewater pH, Fenton's reagents concentrations, initial pollutants concentration, and temperature [97], [99], [102]–[104].

2.2.1 Mechanism of Fenton Process

The main reaction's mechanism could be described by the following set of reactions [49], [90], [103], [105]–[108]:

1- Initiation step:

H_2O_2 decomposition is done due to the catalytic effect of ferrous ions, which results in highly reactive hydroxyl radicals (Eq. 2.11). Then, the resultant ferric ions could be reduced back to ferrous ions using excess H_2O_2 (Eq. 2.12), therefore a cyclic mechanism for ferrous regeneration is taking place through the process.

2- Propagation step:

Although H_2O_2 functions as an initiator according to Eq. 2.11, it also scavenges the hydroxyl radicals as shown in Eq. 2.14, and is generated by Eqs. 2.13 and 2.14.

The presence of organic molecules attracts the hydroxyl radicals to attack these molecules through proton abstraction and produce highly reactive organic radicals (Eq. 2.16). For instance, hydroxyl radicals can break the aromatics and heterocyclic rings as shown in Figure 2.3. Furthermore, organic free radicals are produced in Eqs. 2.18 and 2.19 could be oxidized by Fe^{3+} or reduced by Fe^{2+} .

Figure 2.3 Aromatic Ring-opening due to hydroxyl radical attack

3- Termination step

Hydroxyl radical is the most essential and desired species from this process, therefore optimizing and enhancing the reactions responsible for hydroxyl radical generation is of great importance. Also, decreasing the effect of scavenging reactions must be considered for an efficient and economically viable organic pollutants removal.

2.2.2 Photo Fenton Processes

According to the above mechanism, the synchronization between Eqs. 2.11 and 2.12 are the key to a sustain a Fenton process. However, the rate constant for the reduction reaction (Eq. 2) is found to be in the range of $k = 0.001 - 0.01 M^{-1}s^{-1}$ [109], while the oxidation reaction has a rate constant $k = 76 M^{-1}s^{-1}$ [110] or a value varying between 40 and $80 M^{-1}s^{-1}$ [98], [103]. Accordingly, the reduction reaction is much slower (7000-6000 times slower), therefore it's considered the rate-limiting step in the mechanism [97], [98], [111]. For this reason, the photo Fenton process emerges as a Fenton-based process, where the reaction is enhanced using UV/visible light (Eqs. 2.27 and 2.28). More precisely, the enhancement takes place on the catalysis level in which ferric ions are photo-reduced to ferrous ions, hence promoting the catalyst regeneration and allowing the usage of catalytic amounts of iron salts [97], [102], [112], [113]. Also, it offers better performance at $pH = 3$ when the *hydroxy* – Fe^{3+} complexes are more soluble and $Fe(OH)^{2+}$ is more photoactive [4], [99]. Moreover, photo Fenton process could be done using UV lamps as well as solar light, and this is other advantage from economic point of view.

Harnessing the solar light to enhance the Fenton process has several advantages, but before reaching such a point, plenty of steps and research must be done. Starting from understanding the parameters which are affecting the process and the driving mechanism, then ending with pilot plant design and being ready for integrating photo Fenton process in a full wastewater treatment plant to enhance the biodegradability of the influent entering secondary treatment or polishing and acting as tertiary treatment, to reach the regulatory standards.

2.2.3 Factors Influencing Fenton/Photo Fenton Process Activity

The initial concentration of pollutants, Fenton's reagents concentrations, pH, and the medium temperature are all critical parameters that must be taken care of and optimized to increases the reaction's rate and degradation efficiency.

2.2.3.1 The Initial Concentration of Pollutants

High degradation efficiencies and rates could be achieved by Fenton processes at low initial concentrations of organic pollutants. However, it was found that increasing this concentration decreases the degradation efficiency [97], [99]. For example, K. Dutta et al. found that upon increasing the methylene blue concentration three times, the final degradation efficiency after 240 minutes decreased from complete degradation to 68% [114]. Some solutions proposed for this issue such as increasing hydroxyl radical amount by increasing H_2O_2 and Fe^{2+} initials amounts or by increasing the reaction time [99].

2.2.3.2 The Concentration of Fenton Reagents (Fe^{2+}, H_2O_2)

Essentially, dealing with H_2O_2 as a consumable species and Fe^{2+} as the catalyst is crucial for reaching satisfactory degradation efficiency and operational costs. The final quantitative degradation of the pollutant could be directly linked to the initial concentration of H_2O_2 while the kinetics of the process is directly affected by the amount of iron added [99].

By intuition, H_2O_2 as a consumable species, should be added in stoichiometric proportions with the organic pollutant following the mineralization reaction in which the pollutants is transformed into CO_2 and H_2O . However, due to side and scavenging reactions, excess amounts must be added to account for these losses. Nevertheless, H_2O_2 can't be increased with no limitations for two reasons [97], [99]:

- increasing the operational costs of the process;
- enhancing the $\cdot OH$ scavenging effects are shown in Eqs 2.14 and 2.25

Therefore, an optimum amount for this quantity must be obtained, to sustain an efficient process and have the highest final degradation.

Hydroxyl radicals are produced due to the decomposition of H_2O_2 under the catalytic effect of iron, therefore increasing the amount of the catalyst increases the production of $\cdot OH$. But same as H_2O_2 , it couldn't be increased with no limitations due to increasing the operational costs, while getting lower degradation since enhancement of hydroxyl radical scavenging effect will take place [99], [114].

2.2.3.3 pH

The optimum pH for Fenton/photo Fenton process is found to be between 2.8 and 3.5 [97], [99], [102], [114], [115]. Negative consequences occur for decreasing or increasing the system's pH from the optimum range.

At low pH (< 2.8), hydroxyl radicals scavenging by H^+ take place (Eq. 2.27), therefore the oxidation capacity of the Fenton/photo Fenton process decreases. Moreover, the stability of H_2O_2 in acidic medium increases blocking the decomposition reaction to produce hydroxyl radical [97], [99].

Also, at a high pH value (> 3.5) a decrease in efficiency occurs due to the increased hydrolysis and precipitation of ferric ions in the solution, therefore the catalyst regeneration cycle gets interrupted [97], [99], [114].

Figure 2.4 Speciation diagram of ferric hydroxyl-species as a function of pH [115]

Furthermore, $Fe(II)$ and $Fe(III)$ ions exist in several hydrolyzed species depending on the pH value of the solution. $Fe(II)$ in a pH of 2-7 would mainly present as Fe_{aq}^{2+} , while $Fe(III)$ would present as different species as a function of pH as shown in Figure 2.4 below, accordingly, it could be noticed that at circumneutral pH $Fe(III)$ precipitates as $Fe(OH)_3(s)$ [115].

As mentioned earlier, $Fe(OH)^{2+}$ is the most photoactive species so its occurrence only in this limited acidic range inhibits the usage of the photo Fenton process at neutral pH .

2.2.3.4 Temperature

Carrying the Fenton/photo Fenton process at room temperature is one of the advantages that this AOP offer, however increasing the temperature enhances catalyst regeneration, thereby increasing the degradation efficiency. On the other hand, the temperature can't be increased limitlessly, due to the decomposition of H_2O_2 to water and oxygen in addition to the precipitation of iron ions as ferric hydroxides [99], [114].

2.2.4 Chelating Agents' Usage for Photo Fenton Process Enhancement

Using light to assist the Fenton process for organic pollutants degradation was of huge benefit, however, the pH conundrum still exists. Forcing the operating pH to be in a limited acidic range, therefore acidification and neutralization phases must be added to the process. In this way, additional costs will be added, for this reason extending the working pH region is of great benefit economically and environmentally. In addition to removing these two phases could increase the chances of the photo Fenton process being used on larger scales in the future [116].

By observing Eq. 2.12, one could notice that ferric ions loss due to precipitation at high pH is going to stop the catalyst regeneration, therefore, ceasing the catalytic role of iron and stopping the photo Fenton system. Accordingly, the logical solution is to ensure the dissolution of ferric ions at a wider range of pH to guarantee the permanence of the system till the desired degradation is obtained.

The low efficiency of the photo Fenton process at neutral pH is mainly due to iron precipitation, which could be mitigated by adding a complexing agent [99], [115]. For instance, Wei et al. achieved 95% methylene blue degradation at $pH=7$ in 60 minutes after adding a complexing agent, while only 72% was achieved without adding a complexing agent for the same conditions [117]. The positive impact that chelating agents add to the photo Fenton system are due to [118]:

- promote the activation of hydrogen peroxide and the generation of hydroxyl radicals;
- improve the solubility of nonpolar and lipophilic pollutants;
- enhance the dissolution of iron at neutral pH

Chelating or complexing agents are substances that can form bonds with metal ions, they can be used at high pH to form complexes with the iron species that exist and keep it soluble thus enhancing the production of oxidative species by the continuity of catalytic regeneration in the presence of H_2O_2 [99], [115], [118]–[120].

2.2.4.1 Importance of Photo Fenton-like

It is referred to reactions initiated with ferric ions as “Fenton-like” reactions. Nevertheless, it’s meaningless from a mechanistic standpoint to distinguish “Ferrous” from “Ferric” type reactions [98]. Although, in practice starting with ferrous ions yields a rapid initial degradation, and according to Jiang et al. the Fenton-like reaction appeared to occur much more slowly than the Fenton reaction [98], [121].

Figure 2.5 Comparison of Fenton and Fenton-like reactions for degradation of Acid Black 1 [104]

Also, the same observation was given by Wang’s comparative study, it could be shown from Figure 2.5 that degradation using Fenton was initially faster than Fenton-like [104].

However, starting with ferric ions when using a chelating agent is a must and proven to be more favored for the system and degradation by several researchers [119], [120], [122], [123]. Choosing Fe^{3+} over Fe^{2+} is due to the higher stability constant of the complex formed between ferric ions and chelating agents [120].

The stability constant of a complex is a measure of the strength of interaction between chelating agents and metal ions, in which the higher the stability constant is the higher the tendency of forming the complex will be which is essential for dissolution of the metal ion. For example, the stability constant of Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and ferric ion complex is around 10^{10} larger than that of EDTA and ferrous ion complex. In addition to that, higher stability constants of Fe(III)-complexes suggested higher reaction rates of corresponding Fe(II)-complexes with H_2O_2 [119].

To conclude, according to De Luca et al. The use of iron in the oxidative form of Fe^{2+} did not result in an improvement of the reaction kinetics, in comparison to using Fe^{3+} which is preferable to use with a chelating agent to ensure the stability of the complexes [124].

2.2.4.2 Choice of Chelating Agent

Several Chelating agents exist: Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA); nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA); oxalic acid (OA) and tartaric acid (TA) and all can increase the oxidation of organic pollutants, however, certain criteria must be adopted to choose one of these chelators. The suitable chelate must be:

- less toxic;
- poses high iron-chelation strength;
- resistant to oxidation in the medium application;
- able to facilitate the generation of $\cdot OH$ radicals at neutral pH

EDTA offers a wide range of pH to work with, and according to Clarizia et al. when EDTA has adopted the formation of soluble complexes allows to shift to basic pH values with precipitation of $Fe(III)$ [115]. Accordingly, for this study, the most widely used chelating agent [115], [117], [124], EDTA has been applied to the system.

2.2.5 Choice of Probe Molecule

To simplify experiments and provide more focus on the optimization of both AOPs, one probe molecule will be chosen for the sake of being the recalcitrant pollutants. Although the wastewater effluent in PRPP contains a complex matrix of hazardous organic pollutants, this couldn't be replicated easily. Therefore, one molecule is being used.

Methylene Blue (MB) will be used in all the following experiments as a probe molecule to allow us to test and optimize the AOPs with respect to its color disappearance.

Figure 2.6 Structure of methylene blue molecule

In addition to that, the aromatic-like structure (Figure 2.6) of methylene blue renders it as an applicable probe molecule to substitute actual aromatics that could possess higher toxicity than MB as it was proved that it's only toxic when taken orally so it's relatively safer to work with. MB is known for having a high molar absorptivity, meaning that it can absorb light at a given wavelength, which is $\cong 666nm$ in MB's case

3 Experimental Degradation of Methylene Blue by *ZnO* Photocatalyst and photo Fenton-like Process

This chapter is entitled to present the application of photocatalysis using *ZnO* thin-film, and a photo Fenton-like process at a lab scale. This project aims to investigate each process alone by varying parameters that alter their activity, then examining the possibility of the coupling both techniques is capable of providing an enhanced degradation efficiency and rate.

The first part of this chapter discusses the *ZnO* photocatalysis. the objective is to explore the effect of certain parameters in the preparation process such as precursor's concentration, post-heat treatment temperature, and the number of layers coated, then choose the configuration that provides the highest degradation of MB.

While the second part aims to assess the parameters that affect the photo Fenton-like process such as light, H_2O_2 concentration, catalyst loading, and chelating agent addition, followed by comparing the degradation of the probe molecule by photocatalyst prepared using the configuration chosen from the previous part, photo Fenton-like process, and the coupling of both processes.

Also, this chapter includes the materials and techniques used, a detailed description of the experimental setup, and the analytical method used in the degradation of MB by all processes. It will be ended with the results and discussions regarding each process and their coupling degradation efficiency.

3.1 *ZnO* thin-film on a glass substrate

3.1.1 Materials

- Zinc Acetate Dihydrate (ZAD) (97%), ($MW = 219.5$), from ACROS Organics, Spain.
- 2 – Propanol ($MW = 60.1$) from Fisher Scientific, UK.
- Monoethanolamine (MEA), ($MW = 61.08$), (97%);
- methylene blue powder, ($MW = 319.86$), from Paskem Fine chemical Industries, India;
- microscope glass slide $75 \times 26mm$, $1mm$ thick;
- Deionized water

3.1.2 Techniques Used for the Synthesis and Characterization of *ZnO* Thin-Film

The technique used for accurately depositing a liquid thin-film of the zinc oxide photocatalyst on a glass substrate was dip-coating and that used for the measuring of the absorbance spectrum of the catalyst was the UV-*vis* spectrophotometry.

3.1.2.1 The Dip-coating Technique

The instrument responsible for implementing this technique is called a dip-coater, in this project the latest version of the dip-coater was used, it's from HOLMARC, model: HO-TH-028, shown in figures 3.1 and 3.3. The dip-coating process is separated into three stages:

- 1- Substrate immersion in the precursor solution, where it remains for a certain time
- 2- Substrate withdrawal from the solution at a specified speed
- 3- Solvent evaporation

The dip-coater provides the three above stages and each one has a certain aspect to be controlled through a computer program designed for this model. Using the HOLMARC dip-coater, the glass substrate is lowered down at a constant speed and immersed in the precursor's solution, which is placed in a custom-made Teflon beaker, for an amount of time called dipping time. Afterward, the glass substrate is withdrawn at a constant speed and a thin layer is formed where excess liquid is drained down due to gravity.

The last stage is solvent evaporation, which is done in the dip-coater's heating chamber that is equipped with an infrared heater, which secures a uniform, accurate and easy-drying process of the substrate after each dip.

The Teflon beaker (*Figure 3.1*) is specially designed to dip-coat the glass substrates specified earlier, for the sake of decreasing the volume of prepared sol while still being able to coat the glass efficiently.

Figure 3.1 The HOLMARC Dip Coating Unit Model: HO-TH-02B at ULFG III Laboratory

Moreover, the withdrawal speed is the most dominant parameter within the dip-coating process, and according to its value, the film's thickness is determined (*Figure 3.2*) [125]–[127].

Figure 3.2 The variation of film thickness as a function of withdrawal speed

Figure 3.3 Technical Drawing of the HOLMARC Dip Coating Unit Model: HO-TH-02B

3.1.2.2 The UV/Vis Spectroscopy Technique

The UV/Vis is used to determine the absorbance range of a chemical species as a function of wavelength. In this project, Specord 50 Plus from analytic-jena-Germany was used to determine the absorbance of the synthesized films in the ultraviolet and visible region, also it is used to monitor the degradation of MB by linking the solution's absorbance at a specified wavelength to dye's concentration through Beer-Lambert law.

Ultraviolet and Visible absorption spectrophotometry (Figure 3.3) is a technique based on attenuation of electromagnetic radiation measurement by an absorbing substance [128]. This radiation has a spectral range of 190 – 800 nm. Light from this spectral range impinges on a container, called a cuvette, and placed in the light path of the spectrophotometer. Light passes through the transparent cuvette which contains the sample and hits a photodetector that converts the light energy into an electrical signal, to be analyzed by a computer then shows the result on the screen as absorbance peaks function of light's wavelength. The amount of light hitting the photodetector is reduced due the absorbance of the analyte in the cuvette [129]. The variation of wavelength in the spectrophotometer is done using a monochromator which is an optical device that splits polychromatic light into its component wavelengths, then the slit only allows a very narrow range of wavelengths to pass through the cuvette into the detector. The gradual rotation of the dispersive element allows light

from the whole given spectral range, a small section at a time, to pass through into the cuvette to the detector (Figure 3.4) [130].

Within some limits, the absorbance is proportional to the concentration of the sample being measured. This relationship is called Beer-Lambert law which is shown in Eq. 3.1 below:

$$A = \varepsilon \times L \times c \quad (3.1)$$

Where A represents the absorbance, ε is the molar absorbance coefficient, L is the path length in cm and c is the concentration of the sample [128].

Figure 3.4 Schematic diagram showing the working principle of a UV/Vis spectrophotometer

3.1.2.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

To evaluate the quality of the synthesis that has been done in the lab, SEM was used. This technique provided a clear image of the zinc oxide thin film that had been coated.

SEM is a type of electron microscope that produces several types of signals at the surface of the scanned object when exposed to a high-energy electron beam. The SEM process reveals several traits about the sample such as the chemical composition and the texture of the material. Moreover, the SEM also reveals the crystalline structure, which is the special distribution of the atoms and molecules [131].

The scanning process consists of selecting a certain two-dimensional area with a width ranging from five microns to one centimeter. In some cases, it is possible to perform an SEM on a point located on the surface of the material to determine properties such as the chemical composition or crystal structure [131].

The Figure below demonstrates the setup of the scanning electron microscope. The electron gun at the top of the setup produces the electron beam that is received by the anode below. After that, the beam continues toward the first magnetic condenser lens that converges the beam initially and is responsible for modifying the resolution.

Figure 3.5 Scanning Electron Microscope setup [8]

The second lens, which is known as the objective lens, converges the beam again and focuses it toward the scanned sample. The scanning coil's role is to raster the electron beam on the studied sample (Figure 3.5) [131],[132].

3.1.3 Synthesis Of ZnO Thin-film

As mentioned in the previous chapter, ZnO thin films are to be synthesized by sol-gel method followed with dip-coating technique. This process is formed from three steps, first, preparation of the sol, then coating the glass substrate with the prepared sol, and in the end, post-heat treatment.

3.1.3.1 Preparation of Sol

There exist several parameters responsible for influencing the sol-gel to be prepared, such as type precursor, solvent, and additive. Therefore, the choice of these three elements is a crucial step.

3.1.3.1.1 The Choice of the Precursor

Zinc oxide sols could be fabricated starting from different precursors. However, these precursors could be divided into two families, metal salts and metal alkoxides. Although metal alkoxides offer several chemical advantages, they are hard to deal with in addition to being more expensive. On the other hand, metal salts are cheaper and they offer the facility of use. Moreover, metal salts could divide into two groups: Organic and inorganic salts. The anionic species of the inorganic metal salt is known to be hard to remove from the sol which is not a favorable situation, while the organic group could be eliminated from the sol during the heating treatments [133]. Accordingly, ZAD is used as a precursor in this project because it is the most commonly used precursor from the metal-organic salts group [133].

3.1.3.1.2 The Choice of the Solvent

Due to choosing an inorganic salt, the solvent to be used must have a relatively high dielectric constant to dissolve the precursor, and alcohols are the perfect candidates to choose from. Most used alcohols as solvent are methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, 2-propanol, 1-butanol, and 2-methoxy ethanol. However, ethanol and 2-propanol are the most used ones. 2-propanol was chosen for this as a low boiling point solvent to facilitate efficient evaporation and drying in addition to avoiding crack formation in the post-heat treatment stage [134].

3.1.3.1.3 The Choice of the Additive

ZAD has limited solubility in the solvent chosen, 2-propanol, therefore an additive that is capable of facilitating the dissolution of ZAD in the alcoholic media is needed. Such additive must be able to play the role of chelating and stabilizing ligand that avoids the rapid precipitation of ZAD and secure a stable dispersion to be formed. According to Znaidi, agents like (mono- to tri) ethanolamines could help to obtain this result [133], also, Vajargah et al. showed that monoethanolamine (MEA) is the best stabilizer to achieve a transparent sol-gel grown thin films with proper optical properties [135]. For this reason, MEA, acting as a stabilizer was used in this project.

For the sake of examining the effect of precursor's concentration in the sol, different sols were prepared with concentrations of 0.03, 0.07, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.6 M. Each sol was prepared by dissolving the right amount of ZAD in a 20 ml 2-propanol. After few minutes of magnetically stirring the mixture, MEA was added at a molar ratio $\frac{Zn^{2+}}{MEA} = 1$. Then, the

mixture was kept at 70°C while stirring for one hour. Finally, the clear and transparent ZnO sols were kept to age for 24 hours at ambient conditions.

The temperature of stirring was chosen to be 70°C to avoid the undesired vaporization and minimize evaporation of the essential elements of the sol, such as the stabilizer (MEA , $B.P = 170^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the solvent ($2 - \text{propanol}$, $B.P = 82.5^{\circ}\text{C}$).

3.1.3.2 The Dip-coating Process

As discussed previously, a microscope glass substrate was used as a support. Therefore, cleaning these substrates is the first step to start with. The glass substrates were cleaned with soap, then washed with distilled water followed by ethanol then acetone. The substrates were dried using a microfiber cloth under ambient conditions. The purpose of cleaning the substrates was to remove any contaminants that could influence the film or the sol negatively during the dip-coating process.

The next step is to prepare the dip-coater for the film deposition. First set the substrate in its place, then set up the parameters which control the deposition, and at last set the Teflon beaker after filling it with the sol and the substrate in the favored position to run the dip-coating process. The withdrawal speed was set to 9 mm/s , and this is the maximum speed that could be attained by the dip-coater. The reason behind choosing this high speed is to form an acceptable film thickness, in addition, to avoid stripe defects due to fast evaporation of the solvent during withdrawal (*Figure 3.6*). Stripe defects are due to low withdrawal speeds while evaporation happens faster leaving solid periodic stripes all along the substrate [125], [127], [136].

Figure 3.6 Horizontal lines formation after withdrawal at low speed

After dipping the substrate for 5 seconds, it is withdrawn at the speed mentioned earlier and enters the heating chamber. The temperature of the heating chamber was set to 150°C where the substrate is left for pre-heat treatment for 7 minutes.

For the deposition of several layers, the same procedure is repeated using the same substrate according to the number of layers desired.

3.1.3.3 The Heat Treatment Process

Just after the coating, the substrate enters a heating chamber (figure 3.7 (A)) for pre-heat treatment at a temperature of 150°C for seven minutes. Figure 3.7 (A) below shows the temperature variation in the chamber during the 7 minutes, starting from room temperature. The infrared heater inside the chamber ensures uniform heating to the substrate for uniform drying and evaporation of the solvent.

During this process, the coated substrates by sols of different concentrations were placed in the furnace at a post-heat treatment temperature of 350°C for 1 hour. Also, to examine the effects of post-heat treatment on the activity of ZnO thin-film, the chosen concentration was subjected to four different annealing temperatures $250, 350, 450,$ and 550°C for one hour.

After one hour of placing the substrate at the desired temperature, it is left in the furnace (Figure 3.7 (B)) until it fully cools to avoid opening the furnace at high temperature and damaging both the substrate and furnace due to sudden high-temperature difference.

Notice that before reaching the desired temperature, the substrate is subjected to a temperature rise in the furnace at a rate of $46^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ as shown in Figure 3.7 (B) below.

Figure 3.7 : (A): Temperature profile inside the heating chamber of the dip coater during pre-heat treatment (top), drawing of the dip-coaters heating chamber internals (bottom) (B): Temperature profile inside the furnace during post-heat treatment (top), the ceramic internals of the furnace used for post heat treatment with heating electric heating coils on the sides (bottom)

3.1.4 Photocatalytic Degradation of Methylene Blue by ZnO thin-film

In this part of the chapter, the experimental setup and analytic method used to monitor the photocatalysis process are shown. Followed by the results and discussion section where the optical and microstructural properties of the synthesized ZnO thin films, in addition to the effects of the varied parameter, are all to be discussed.

3.1.4.1 Experimental Setup

Each coated substrate was dipped in a 50 ml beaker containing 42.5 ml of water with 3 ppm MB. As a source of light, a UV lamp emitting radiation with wavelength 365 nm was used for all the experiments. The angle of the substrate in each beaker was adjusted to ensure the maximum exposure of the substrate's surface to the UV irradiations.

After 1 hour from placing the substrates in the beaker, the first recording was taken which is going to be labeled as t_0 . The reason behind that is to allow the adsorption of pollutants on the catalyst's surface to take place.

After measuring the absorbance at t_0 of the samples taken from each beaker, the UV lamp is turned on and a sample is taken every 30 minutes for the next 8 hours.

3.1.4.2 Analytical Methods

The course of the photocatalysis was monitored by following the absorption value at wavelength 666 nm, which is chosen from the set of values that MB is known to have a peak at (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8 The absorption of a 10 μ M methylene blue in the UV/Visible range

The results of the experiments were plotted as degradation efficiency and rate of MB. By using spectrophotometry, the results are given as absorption versus the wavelength. As mentioned earlier in this chapter the Beer-Lambert law allows the shift from absorption of the sample to analyte's concentration, therefore if:

$$A_0 = \varepsilon \times L \times C_0 \quad (3.2)$$

and:

$$A = \varepsilon \times L \times C \quad (3.3)$$

Therefore:

$$\frac{A}{A_0} = \frac{\varepsilon \times L \times C}{\varepsilon \times L \times C_0} = \frac{C}{C_0} \quad (3.4)$$

To study the photocatalysis kinetic, the degradation rate is plotted as the natural logarithm of the ratio C/C_0 as a function of time using Eq. 3.6.

$$\ln\left(\frac{C}{C_0}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{A}{A_0}\right) \quad (3.5)$$

Pseudo-first-order kinetics is shown in Eq. 3.7.

$$r = -\frac{dC}{dt} = K \times C \quad (3.6)$$

Simple integration of this equation (with the same boundary conditions $C = C_0$ at $t = 0$), gives the expected equation (Eq. 3.8):

$$\ln\left(\frac{C}{C_0}\right) = K \times t \quad (3.7)$$

where $t = \text{time in minutes}$

Then the degradation efficiency (%X) could be calculated by Eq. 3.9 below, and plotted with respect to time:

$$\%X = \left(1 - \frac{A}{A_0}\right) \times 100 = \left(1 - \frac{C}{C_0}\right) \times 100$$

$A_0 = \text{sample's absorption at } t_0$

$A = \text{sample's absorption at } t$

$C_0 = \text{MB concentration at } t_0$

$C = \text{MB concentration at } t$

(3.8)

3.1.4.3 Results and Discussion

3.1.4.3.1 Optical Properties of ZnO Thin-film

Thirteen substrates of the ZnO photocatalyst were prepared, five of them referred to the variation in ZAD's concentration, whereas the other four correspond to the variation in the post-heat treatment temperature and the other four correspond to multi-layer thin-film. The measurement of the absorption spectra of these substrates is highly significant to monitor the increase or decrease in it upon changing parameters that influence the catalyst's surface and structure. The prepared ZnO thin films were measured through the UV-vis spectrometer and were found to have an absorption range between 300-400nm due to the high absorption of ZnO in the UV-A region corresponding to its E_g compatibility with this region.

To visualize the importance of heat treatment, absorption of a one-layer *ZnO* thin-film had been measured before post-heat treatment (after pre-heat treatment at 150°C) and after post-heat treatment at 350°C. Figure 3.9 shows these results:

Figure 3.9 The absorbance (a.u.) of *ZnO* one layer photocatalyst before and after post-heat treatment at 350°C

These results show the huge increase in absorption at the 300 nm to 400 nm after post-heat treatment has been applied. This might be due to the high-temperature effect on granular growth and increasing crystallinity of the particles, in addition to that completely removing all the impurities such as the solvent and the acetate group coming from the organic metal salt used to provide the precursor.

To further create a hypothesis roaming around the possible influence of alternating the post-heat treatment temperatures might have on the photocatalytic degradation, the substrates post-heat treated at 250, 350, 450, and 550°C were measured in the spectrophotometer and the absorption results are shown in Figure 3.10

Figure 3.10 The absorbance (a.u.) of *ZnO* photocatalyst post-heat treated at four different temperatures

The resulting absorbance of the catalyst substrates at different temperatures was very obvious stating that the higher the annealing temperature is, the higher will be the catalyst absorption, therefore, indicating an improved crystallinity and granular growth of the catalyst particles. However, at a certain limit (550°C) this absorption shifted downward along with the whole wavelength range. Therefore, temperatures above a certain boundary negatively affect the *UV* range absorption of the film and by that, its crystallinity and morphology.

Also, to formulate a hypothesis regarding the effect of coating multiple layers on photocatalytic degradation, the 1, 3, 5, 7 layers *ZnO* thin-film substrates were measured in the spectrophotometer and the absorption results are shown in Figure 3.11 below. The graph shows what the higher the number of layers is, the greater the absorption at the wavelength range [300 nm, 400 nm]. Therefore it's predicted that the seven layers will be able to demonstrate a high photocatalytic degradation toward MB.

Figure 3.11 (A): The absorbance (a.u.) of multi-layered *ZnO* thin film with different number of layers, (B): Glass substrate coated with 7 layers of *ZnO* photocatalyst, then post-heat treated at 450°C

3.1.4.3.2 Microstructural properties of *ZnO* thin film

Figure 3.12 below shows the SEM micrographs of a one-layer *ZnO* thin-film. The observed film wrinkling in this study is a consequence of the chemical evolution of the *ZnO* network driven by the application of a specific pre-heat treatment. For instance, applying adequate synthesis procedure conditions and precursors in the right order is of great importance, because at the pre-nucleation state, the dip-coated film is still an elastic gel retaining a certain amount of the organic molecules (2 – *propanol*, MEA, acetic acid, soluble acetate, and complex MEA-acetate group) [137].

Figure 3.12 (A): SEM micrograph of ZnO thin film at a $2\mu\text{m}$ scale, (B) SEM micrograph of ZnO thin film at a 500nm scale

Once the dipped glass substrate enters the Infrared (IR) pre-heating chamber, the film drying proceeds from the top, turning the upper surface into a rigid skin with a much higher elastic modulus than the viscous interior, wherein the solvent vapor is building up and the skin becomes prone to bending [138].

3.1.4.3.3 Effect of precursor's concentration

The photodegradation rate and efficiency of MB under *UV* light ($\lambda = 365\text{ nm}$) for the five concentrations $0.03, 0.07, 0.1, 0.2, 0.6\text{ M}$ over ZnO thin-film is shown in figures 3.13 and 3.14.

Figure 3.13 below shows the values of K for the tested concentrations along with the regression coefficients. The apparent pseudo-first-order rate constants K obtained, are related to the precursor's concentration ($[\text{ZAD}]$) in the sol.

Figure 3.13 Comparative photodegradation kinetics of $10\mu\text{M}$ methylene blue by ZnO thin films coated with sols of different precursor's concentration with *UV* light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$

It was observed also that the degradation rate and efficiency (Figure 3.14) kept increasing with the increase of precursor's concentration from 0.03 M to 0.1 M , then it started to

decrease with the increase of concentration. This observation could be confirmed through what was mentioned in chapter 2 regarding the catalyst dosage influence on the photocatalytic activity.

Therefore, above a certain limit, the catalyst dosage negatively affects the photodegradation of MB by ZnO thin films, and for this system, the limit concentration was found to be 0.1M, where the highest degradation efficiency (82.6%) and rate ($K = -0.0036 \text{ min}^{-1}$) is reached. For this reason, in the next experiments, ZnO thin films used, are synthesized using a sol with a ZAD concentration of 0.1 M.

Figure 3.14 Final degradation of 10µM methylene blue by ZnO thin films coated with sols of different precursor's concentration with UV light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$

3.1.4.3.4 Effect of Post-heat Treatment Temperature

In this experiment, the photodegradation of methylene was done using four ZnO thin films of 0.1 M concentration, but each film is post-treated with a different temperature.

According to figure 3.15 below, the degradation rate of methylene blue increases as the post-heat treatment temperature increases till it reaches 450°C, after which, this rate decreases with the temperature decrease.

Figure 3.15 Comparative photodegradation kinetics of 10µM methylene blue by ZnO thin films post-heat treated at different temperatures with UV light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$

Also, these reactions still follow pseudo-first-order kinetics, and the Figure above shows the values of K for the tested temperatures along with the regression coefficients. The apparent pseudo-first-order rate constants K obtained, are related to the post-heat treatment temperature of ZnO thin films.

Moreover, the degradation efficiency of *ZnO* thin-film post-heat treated at 450°C (89.7%) was found to be the greatest compared to other thin films treated at other temperatures ([250,75.25%]; [350,85.37%]; [550,85.16%]). Therefore, post-heat treatment at 450°C for 1 hour, appears to be the optimum temperature in these conditions for the photocatalytic degradation of MB.

This could be confirmed by what was mentioned by Zhang et al. According to him, increasing post-heat treatment temperature increases the photoactivity of the catalyst due to the enhanced crystallization and the removal of unwanted impurities. However, increasing this temperature above a certain limit decreases the photoactivity due to pores collapse at very high temperatures therefore the catalyst's surface area decreases [72]. In addition to that, the absorbance of the film decreased with the increase of post-heat treatment temperature. Therefore, the effect of post-heat treatment on photocatalytic activity could be predicted through the optical properties of the *ZnO* thin film

3.1.4.3.5 Degradation of methylene blue using multi-layered *ZnO* thin films

For this experiment, the optimized parameters above (0.1 M precursor's concentration and 450°C post-heat treatment temperature) were used to synthesize multi-layered *ZnO* thin films on glass substrates. Then these films were utilized for the photodegradation of MB using UV radiation ($\lambda = 365 \text{ nm}$). The degradation rate and efficiency are shown in figures 3.16 and 3.17.

As seen in figure 3.16, increasing the number of layers doesn't affect the pseudo-first-order kinetics of the photocatalyst, however, the photodegradation of MB using a 3-layer *ZnO* thin-film appeared to have the highest rate.

Figure 3.16 Comparative photodegradation kinetics of 10 μM methylene blue by *ZnO* multilayered thin films with UV light of $\lambda=365 \text{ nm}$

Degradation efficiency (Figure 3.17) and the rate was as follows: $3 > 7 > 5 > 1$, therefore the hypothesis formulated earlier depending on the absorption spectrum of the films wasn't valid. In addition to that, the difference in photocatalytic activity between the multi-layered films is very small. Therefore, one could assume with these results, no additional advantage is gained after coating three layers with the followed procedure and the concentration of the photocatalytic materials is increasing but such increase has a negative effect on the photocatalytic degradation

Figure 3.17 Comparative photodegradation efficiency of methylene blue by ZnO multilayered thin films with UV light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$

According to Saurdi et al., as the thickness increased above a certain limit agglomerated particles started to appear. In addition to that, increasing the number of layers increased the packing density of the ZnO thin-film whereby the best structure of particles was observed at the determined limit.

3.1.5 Conclusion

In summary, Using the procedure and parameters described above, the optimum multi-layer ZnO thin-film coated on a glass substrate to remove MB is the one synthesized from a sol with $[ZAD] = 0.1\text{ M}$, 3 layers, coated using 9mm/s withdrawal velocity and pre-heat treated at 150°C for 7 minutes each layer, and post-heat treated at 450°C for 1 hour at atmospheric pressure.

This configuration is going to be used to synthesize the film to be utilized in the coupling with photo Fenton-like process.

3.2 Photo Fenton-Like Process for Methylene Blue Degradation at Neutral pH

3.2.1 Materials

- iron (III) nitrate nonahydrate, 99+%, for analysis, ACROS Organics, ($MW = 404 \text{ g/mol}$)
- Hydrogen peroxide solution 30% (w/w), Riedel de Haën;
- Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, (EDTA), dipotassium magnesium salt dihydrate, extra pure, ($MW = 426.76 \text{ g/mol}$), Sharlau

3.2.2 Experimental Setup

In this section, all the experiments were carried out in a batch reactor using 50 ml beakers, under UV light of wavelength $\lambda = 365\text{nm}$. Also, the MB concentration was fixed at 10 ppm, since the effect of increasing the contaminant concentration in the Fenton process has been well discussed and studied by several researchers.

Moreover, the main focus for this study was to optimize the probe molecule degradation in a neutral medium ($pH = 7$), therefore the pH of the MB and water was kept at 7-8 before the addition of the Fenton process reagents.

In the batch reactors, 50 ml water and 10 ppm MB was added, followed by the needed concentration of H_2O_2 and finally the Fe^{3+} addition to marking the start of the reaction. Aliquots were withdrawn from the reactors at selected intervals for spectrophotometric analysis. The concentration of the MB at different times was obtained by measuring the absorption at $\lambda = 666\text{nm}$. The same analytical method used in the photocatalyst section was used here.

3.2.3 Results and Discussion

Several experiments were done to examine the behavior and assess the photo Fenton-like capabilities. In this section, the main focus was to reach the best configuration of the photo Fenton-like process in terms of degradation without using excess material and trying to reach the highest efficiency and activity at the least quantities possible at a neutral pH.

The parameters studied were the light effect, the concentration of Fenton's reagents, and the addition of a chelating agent. After finding the needed configuration, it is utilized to be used in the coupling process with the previously studied ZnO multi-layered thin-film.

3.2.3.1 Effect of Light

The photo Fenton process is well known for being more active and enhanced due to the added value which light offers to the mechanism. The catalyst regeneration by the aid of light increases the capabilities of undergoing reaction to remove recalcitrant pollutants.

To show the light's effect, two batch reactors containing 50 ml water with 10 ppm MB, and 1 ppm Fe^{3+} , while H_2O_2 was added according to the following molar ratio $\frac{H_2O_2}{Fe^{3+}}=700$.

At this ratio H_2O_2 concentration is slightly above the stoichiometric amount needed to degrade the 10 ppm of MB. The stoichiometric quantity could be calculated from the following reaction (Eq. 3.9) [139].

Figure 3.18 visualize the effect of light presence and absence on the Fenton-like process. The photo Fenton-like process is 60 times faster than the Fenton-like process. The reason that could be proposed to explain the low activity of the Fenton-like process at these conditions is the initial pH which is neutral, therefore with the addition of Fe^{3+} the formation of $Fe(OH)_3$ will be favored leading, which is going to precipitate at this pH to catalyst activity loss [115].

Figure 3.18 Comparative degradation rate of 10 ppm methylene blue using Fenton like and photo Fenton like process with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$

Also, the photo Fenton-like process, reached 43% degradation efficiency while the Fenton-like process (no light) reached only 0.952% efficiency. This shows clearly the benefits of using light to enhance catalyst regeneration.

3.2.3.2 Effect of H_2O_2 concentration

H_2O_2 is being consumed through the process by several reactions, desired reactions, and scavenging reactions. Therefore, finding the right quantity is favored economically for any Fenton process. Figures 3.19 and 3.20 represents the degradation efficiency and rate for different $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]}$ molar ratios, knowing that the mass concentration of $Fe^{3+} = 1 ppm$.

In Figure 3.19 below, the degradation efficiencies increase as the $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]}$ ratio increases; however, the degradation efficiency increase is small at high ratios. Accordingly, increasing the $[H_2O_2]$ at a constant $[Fe^{3+}]$ will reach a level at which additional amounts of H_2O_2 have little or no effect on the degradation efficiency. Even though at high $[H_2O_2]$ high degradation efficiencies are reached, but it's economically unfavorable.

Figure 3.19 Comparative degradation efficiency of 10 ppm methylene blue by different $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]}$ ratios at different times (120, 240, 480) minutes with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$

In Figure 3.20 below, also it was observed that the increase in $[H_2O_2]$ increased the degradation rate, where the reactions followed pseudo-first-order kinetics except for $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]} = 40000$, and all the apparent kinetic rate constants are increasing with $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]}$

Although the greatest rate has been reached by the highest ratio, adopting such values for the degradation of calcitrant organic pollutants increases the operational costs for a small additional rate. Therefore, such investment is not feasible and a good amount of H_2O_2 that balances the reaction time and economics to avoid paying for $\cdot OH$ scavengers.

Figure 3.20 Comparative degradation rates of 10 ppm methylene blue by different $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]}$ ratios with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$

By finding the ratio between the rate constant difference and the difference between the corresponding $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]}$ (Eq. 3.10) one could see the amount of degradation rate increase for a unit ratio increase therefore the optimal concentration is going to be the highest value that represents the highest degradation rate increase with the lowest added $[H_2O_2]$.

$$s = \frac{K_{r_2} - K_{r_1}}{r_2 - r_1}$$

where K_{r_n} = rate constant at ratio r_n (3.10)

$$r_n = \frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]}$$

Then, the results of applying this equation are presented in Figure 3.21 below:

Figure 3.21 The values of s found by Eq. 3.10

Accordingly, the slope between ratios 500 and 700 is the greatest, therefore the highest degradation rate increase achieved with the minimum amount of H_2O_2 is found to be when using $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]} = 700$, knowing that the mass concentration of $Fe = 1 \text{ ppm}$.

For this reason, the $[H_2O_2]$ that will be used in the next experiments is the same amount used to reach a molar ratio of $\frac{[H_2O_2]}{[Fe^{3+}]} = 700$

3.2.3.3 Effect of Fe^{3+} concentration effect

In this experiment, the effect of increasing $[Fe^{3+}]$ on degradation efficiency and the rate was examined, then an optimum value was chosen to be used later.

In figure 3.22, it is observed that increasing the iron concentration from 1 ppm to 15 ppm increased the degradation efficiency, however, this increase was slower at higher values of $[Fe^{3+}]$. Therefore, there exists a value that could be considered an optimum to our system which provides the highest activity with the minimum amount possible.

Figure 3.22 Comparative degradation efficiency of 10 ppm methylene blue by different Fe^{3+} concentrations with UV light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$

Also, one could notice that after one hour the increase in degradation efficiency was very small. Therefore, the reaction could be considered as finished after one hour. Then figure 3.23 which represents the degradation rate plots $\ln\left(\frac{C}{C_0}\right)$ for the first hour only.

Figure 3.23 Comparative degradation rate of 10 ppm methylene blue by different Fe^{3+} concentrations with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$

Depending on the kinetics data shown in figure 3.23, the reactions followed the pseudo-first-order kinetics for the first hour only, then a suspension of solid particles started to form in the reactors due to the neutral pH .

Figure 3.24 below, shows a top view of the inside of two reactors where Fe^{3+} concentrations have been varied (1ppm, 10 ppm) after one hour from starting the experiment.

Figure 3.24 Top view of (A) photo Fenton-like batch reactor with 1 ppm Fe^{3+} , (B) photo Fenton-like batch reactor with 10 ppm Fe^{3+} after one hour from starting the degradation of 10 ppm methylene blue with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$

In A, a clear blue solution is observed, while solid precipitates are observed in B. Sludge is observed starting from 10 ppm of Fe^{3+} as initial concentration.

According to the literature and mechanism mentioned earlier, iron is the catalytic species in this reaction. Therefore, catalytic amounts should be added to reach acceptable degradation rates and efficiencies at a reasonable operational cost. Therefore, it is chosen 10 ppm to be used as the Fe^{3+} concentration for the rest of the experiments because it's the lowest concentration at which iron sludge is formed and an acceptable degradation rate and efficiency are obtained.

3.2.3.4 Addition of Chelating Agent

For the sake of enhancing the photo Fenton-like process in a neutral medium, this experiment is dedicated to showing the effect of adding the chelating agent Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). And as mentioned earlier it was added at a molar ratio $Fe^{3+}:EDTA = 1$ for the sake of decreasing the costs with maintaining an acceptable degradation.

The two reactions were done with the H_2O_2 concentration was chosen from before, 10 ppm of Fe^{3+} and 10 ppm EDTA to degrade 10 ppm MB.

Figure 3.25 below clearly shows that EDTA enhanced the degradation rate of the system by allowing Fe^{3+} photoactive species to remain soluble at neutral pH. The degradation rate constant had approximately doubled, this shows that without using EDTA high amounts of the added iron are being ineffective at neutral pH.

Figure 3.25 Comparative degradation rate of 10ppm methylene blue using Photo Fenton-like and Photo Fenton-like with EDTA with UV light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$ during the first one hour of the experiment

The modification of the photo Fenton-like system with EDTA had a positive impact on both degradation rate and efficiency therefore it's considered successful. Also, at 90 minutes photo Fenton-like with EDTA was able to reach a 91.5% degradation efficiency while the same process with no EDTA had reached 66.8%. Therefore, the usage of EDTA has proved to be capable of protecting Fenton's catalyst from precipitation due to neutral pH.

3.2.3.5 Effect of temperature

In this experiment, the photo Fenton like the experiment was done at two different temperatures (23°C and 30°C) and the used concentrations: 10 ppm Fe^{3+} , $59\text{ ppm H}_2\text{O}_2$ and 10 ppm MB with UV light of $\lambda = 365\text{ nm}$. As seen in figure 3.26 below, the increase of temperature from 23°C to 30°C greatly increased the rate of the photo Fenton-like process. However, after the first hour, the experiment done at 30°C shows a decrease in the rate. This is due to the formation of Fe^{3+} precipitates while the photo Fenton-like experiment done at 23°C didn't show much change in its kinetics.

Figure 3.26 Comparative degradation rate of 10ppm methylene blue using Photo Fenton-like at two temperatures(23°C and 30°C) with UV light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$

According to literature, the consequences of high temperature were H_2O_2 decomposition into oxygen and water, and iron loss due to precipitation. Although the iron loss was reported to occur at a temperature above 50°C [140], in this experiment, it was lower than that (30°C). The reason could be the neutral pH that is being adapted for all our experiments which also facilitates the iron loss due to precipitation.

Therefore, the temperature is an important factor and it is favored to perform the photo Fenton-like reactions at a temperature optimum between operation costs and the performance of the process. For the coupling experiment, temperature = 23°C was chosen to avoid the effect of iron loss while still having an acceptable activity.

3.2.4 Conclusion

After examining the photo Fenton-like system and studying its parameters, the optimum configuration for the conditions followed in this project are 59 ppm of H_2O_2 , 10 ppm of Fe^{3+} and EDTA addition at a molar ratio $\text{Fe}^{3+}:\text{EDTA} = 1$, in addition to the operating temperature of 23°C . This configuration is going to be used in the coupling experiment later to evaluate its capabilities.

3.3 Coupling

For the sake of the main purpose of the project which is the coupling, the next experiment was comparing the capabilities of four systems, *ZnO* multi-layered thin-film which was optimized earlier, photo Fenton-like, and the coupling of both.

3.3.1 Results and Discussion

The main objective behind this experiment is to examine the existence of synergistic effect between the *ZnO* photocatalyst and the Fenton process, and if so, could this coupling be able to reach a degradation such as the degradation provided by photo Fenton-like system which was modified with *EDTA*.

Figure 3.27 summarizes the degradation efficiency and rate of 10 ppm MB using three systems: Photo Fenton-like (, multi-layered *ZnO* thin-film, and coupling between both. The used photocatalyst is the optimized 3 layers *ZnO* thin film, and for the photo-Fenton process the optimized configuration (10 ppm of Fe^{3+} , 59 ppm of H_2O_2 , 23° C) and 10 ppm *EDTA* for the coupling with *EDTA*.

Figure 3.27 (A): comparative degradation efficiency, and (B): comparative degradation rate of 10 ppm methylene blue using Photo Fenton-like, *ZnO* photocatalyst and the coupling of both with UV light of $\lambda=365nm$

As seen in Figure 3.27 (A), the coupling between both AOPs resulted in a degradation efficiency of 87.7% after 8 hours, while each system was capable to reach 69% for the Fenton system alone and 61% for the photocatalyst system alone.

As for the rate, Figure 3.27 (B) represents the plotting of $\ln\left(\frac{C}{C_0}\right)$ and the apparent rate constant of the process and it appears that the three processes follow pseudo-first-order kinetics. The degradation rate of MB using the coupled system is greater than each system alone, therefore the coupling of the two AOPs proved to be successful. There are several reasons behind this enhancement, it might be simply that now there are two sources of hydroxyl radicals, or the catalyst regeneration is being facilitated and fortified by the electron-hole pairs formed by the photocatalyst.

However, coupling the photo Fenton-like system modified with *EDTA* didn't enhance the degradation. Figure 3.28 shows the change in the kinetics of this system and the behavior of this system at different time intervals

Figure 3.28 Comparative degradation rate from (A): 0 to 60 minutes, (B): 90 to 270 minutes, (C): 300 to 480 minutes of 10 ppm MB using photo Fenton-like, ZnO photocatalyst and coupling of both with and without EDTA with UV light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$

As seen above, the addition of *EDTA* to the coupling system at a molar ratio $Fe^{3+} : EDTA = 1$ didn't give the same effect as with the addition of *EDTA* to the photo Fenton-like process alone. However, the new system exhibited three behaviors A, B, and C, at three different time intervals. First, for time = [0,60] minutes (A), the coupled system with EDTA had the same degradation rate as the coupled system without EDTA. Then for time = [90,270] (B), the rate decreased and became similar to the photo Fenton-like system alone, and finally, for time = [300,480] (C), it behaved approximately as the photocatalyst system alone.

Accordingly, *EDTA* function was inhibited and wasn't able to give results in the coupled system same as the results with the photo Fenton-like system alone. Figure 3.29 below shows the color difference and degradation efficiencies of samples from the performed reactions after 8 hours.

Figure 3.29 Comparative photograph showing samples from each process and the degradation efficiencies of 10 ppm methylene blue with UV light with UV light of $\lambda=365\text{nm}$

From this figure, it could be seen that methylene blue completely disappeared by the use of a photo Fenton-like process modified with *EDTA*. Also, the coupling reached an acceptable degradation efficiency (87.7%). The coupling system was able to increase methylene blue degradation, and it might be due to the creation of electron-hole pairs where the iron catalyst is getting benefit from to facilitate its regeneration.

3.3.2 Conclusion

Coupling of the optimized photocatalyst with the optimized photo Fenton system proved to be efficient in the degradation of MB more than the photocatalyst and the Fenton process alone. Although *EDTA* greatly enhanced the photo Fenton-like process, surprisingly that wasn't the case in the coupled system. Therefore, regarding this issue, a choice has to be, using a coupled system that offers a good degradation and low environmental impact, or adding more organic chemicals such as *EDTA* to gain excellent degradation. This choice needs an assessment for the composition of the water to be treated, in addition to a study for the costs and impacts of each technique is used.

Conclusion and Future Perspectives

PRPP wastewater is being treated through the primary secondary and tertiary wastewater treatment techniques, but there still exist several recalcitrant organic pollutants that are characterized by their detrimental effects on human health and the environment, in addition to their ability to survive against conventional treatment methods. For this reason, researchers have investigated the AOPs as the route for a clean water source. From here, photocatalysis and photo Fenton processes are implemented, not to extract, separate, or remove, but to devastate and degrade toxicants.

This innovative, highly effective, and relatively cheap technology was conducted by this project and was done at the Lab of Petroleum in the Lebanese University, Faculty of Engineering. This work focuses on the optimization and development of the heterogeneous thin-film photocatalysis and photo Fenton process for the degradation of MB.

Optimization of the photocatalyst catalyst was done by three approaches. The first one aimed to observe the influence of changing the precursor's concentration on film properties and how these properties in turn affected the degradation efficiencies where 0.1M emerged as the optimum concentration for an excellent photocatalytic performance. Whereas, the second approach took the optimized concentration and focused on varying the post-heat treatment temperatures that in turn changed the microstructure of the catalyst. The most appealing post-heat treatment temperature that showed the highest degradation efficiency was 450°C. Finally, the third approach examined the capabilities of multi-layered thin films treated and synthesized using the chosen parameters above and their degradation activity. The most active substrate was the three layers coated thin-film substrate.

The photo Fenton-like process was studied at neutral pH . Effects of light, Fenton's reagents, and chelating agent addition have been studied. The UV light ($\lambda = 365\text{ nm}$) greatly enhanced the reactions. For the Fenton's reagents, as $[H_2O_2]$ and $[Fe^{3+}]$ increases the degradation rate and efficiency increases, 59 ppm H_2O_2 and 10 ppm Fe^{3+} are chosen as optimum concentrations. Also, chelating agent ($EDTA$) had a great improvement on the photo Fenton process after being added at a molar ratio $Fe^{3+}:EDTA = 1$. In the end, coupling of the photocatalysis system and photo Fenton-like system has been done. The coupled system had a degradation efficiency greater than both systems alone, while the addition of a chelating agent to the coupled system decreases the degradation drastically.

As for future perspectives, after proving the capabilities of this coupled system, could be used to simulate using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) to simulate then design a photoreactor that utilizes the solar radiations. This route allows the scale-up of this process as a potential technology for treating recalcitrant organic pollutants. Also, coupling the Fenton process and the photocatalytic process could be designed as a combination of two heterogeneous catalysts to increase the process productivity and easiness.

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